

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 3.5

Comparazione economica dei costi degli interventi proposti rispetto quelli usuali.

NOVEMBRE 2025

Poročilo 3.5

Primerjava stroškov utrjevanja po metodi CONSTRAIN in s klasično metodo

NOVEMBER 2025

Authors: Gattesco N.⁽¹⁾, Boem I.⁽¹⁾, Rizzi E.⁽¹⁾, Saveri M.⁽²⁾, Aiello A.⁽²⁾, Faganel A.⁽²⁾, Gams M.⁽³⁾, Dudine A.⁽⁴⁾, Hafner R.⁽⁵⁾, Peršolja I.⁽⁵⁾, Gostič S.⁽⁶⁾

(1) Department of Engineering and Architecture, University of Trieste (Italy)

(2) ATER Udine, Udine (Italy) (3) Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)

(4) Fibre Net Spa, Pavia di Udine (Italy) (5) ZVKDS, Ljubljana (Slovenia) (6) ZRMK, Ljubljana (Slovenia)

www.ita-slo.eu/pro-sis

<https://www.facebook.com/61556327101140>

<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/interreg-italia-slovenija-pro-sis>

PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 3.5 Economic comparison of proposed interventions costs versus usual costs

NOVEMBER 2025

Authors: Gattesco N.⁽¹⁾, Boem I.⁽¹⁾, Rizzi E.⁽¹⁾, Saveri M.⁽²⁾, Aiello A.⁽²⁾, Faganel A.⁽²⁾, Gams M.⁽³⁾, Dudine A.⁽⁴⁾, Hafner R.⁽⁵⁾, Peršolja I.⁽⁵⁾, Gostič S.⁽⁶⁾

(1) Department of Engineering and Architecture, University of Trieste (Italy)

(2) ATER Udine, Udine (Italy) (3) Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)

(4) Fibre Net Spa, Pavia di Udine (Italy) (5) ZVKDS, Ljubljana (Slovenia) (6) ZRMK, Ljubljana (Slovenia)

www.ita-slo.eu/pro-sis

<https://www.facebook.com/61556327101140>

<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/interreg-italia-slovenija-pro-sis>

Report 3.5

Economic comparison of proposed interventions costs vs. usual costs

Summary

1. Introduction	3
2. Abstract	4
3. Overview	6
4. The overall scale of the problem: seismic risk	11
4.1. Seismic hazard in the programme area	11
4.2. Exposure of the programme area and comparisons with national data	17
4.2.1. Population density	17
4.2.2. Economic value of buildings	19
4.2.3. Considerations on cultural heritage	26
4.3. Vulnerability of real estate in the program area	32
4.3.1. Evolution of Italian seismic regulations	33
4.3.2. Construction periods and state of conservation of buildings	37
5. The economic dimension of seismic risk and measures to reduce it	1
5.1. Costs to reduce seismic risk and impact on the national economy	1
5.2. Impact of interventions on the national economy (input-output matrices)	4
5.3. Dynamics of the construction sector and government incentives	7
5.4. Reasons for the modest interest in seismic safety	11
5.5. Comparison between traditional and CONSTRAIN technologies	14
6. Conclusions	19
Acknowledgments	19
Appendix 1	20
Appendix 2	25

ANNEXES:

- A) Example of price analyses
- B) Bill of quantities for the strengthening of the building of ATER in Udine by using the CONSTRAIN technology
- C) Bill of quantities for the strengthening of the building of ATER in Udine by using the traditional "rete-betoncino" technology

1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 3.5 of the “PRO-SIS” project, titled “Cost comparison between reinforcement interventions using “CONSTRAIN” techniques and those involving reinforcement interventions with commonly used techniques”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extensive experimental campaign. The strengthening method developed is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced with fibre-based composite materials. The main advantage of this system is that it can be applied to only one side of the wall, making it much more convenient for residents and businesses. As construction work can be carried out only on the exterior of the building, people and their belongings do not have to be relocated, and business activity does not have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the interior (or exterior, when interior application is preferred). The strengthening method stands out due to its proven effectiveness in tests on structural components and a full-scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for designing and applying these strategies. To this end, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated against the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide designers with robust strategies for designing the proposed systems, as well as instructions for design in commonly used commercial structural design programmes.

The purpose of this REPORT 3.5 is to examine the economic and social impact of using seismic risk reduction technology based on pultruded mesh applied to one side of walls, developed in the CONSTRAIN projects¹.

¹ Hereinafter referred to simply as “CONSTRAIN technology”

2. Abstract

The analysis began by assessing the need for seismic retrofitting of buildings. Once this need was established, the analysis focused on the causes hindering the retrofitting work and possible solutions to the problem. First, the following is established:

- Seismic retrofitting works are necessary in regions – such as the Interreg ITA-SI programme area, but also applicable to others – that exhibit all of the following:
 - Areas have high or medium seismic risk;
 - A significant proportion of buildings was constructed before seismic standards were developed;
 - A clear prevalence of residential building renovation over new construction.
- People are reluctant to move out for the duration of the construction work.

The study revealed that CONSTRAIN technology can overcome the problem of relocation, a major obstacle to carrying out the work. This is because it can guarantee an adequate level of earthquake resistance by acting only on the external part of buildings, allowing the work to be carried out without the need to relocate the occupants of buildings undergoing seismic strengthening.

Even if it is not necessary to relocate residents, they are not very keen to undertake costly and demanding work for a risk that can only be assessed probabilistically. Additionally, strengthening individual houses would not significantly alter the overall seismic risk profile of a region. However, this can be mitigated through public intervention in building works. Public intervention – not only ensuring the safety of occupants and improving the condition of public assets – is appropriate for several reasons, including the substantial difference between the cost of preventive strengthening compared to post earthquake repair, as already noted several times in the Programme Area.

However, it is necessary to consider that, in the case of public building works, the economic and social-health costs of the works carried out using the various available methods are of decisive importance. For this reason, it was necessary to compare the costs of the “rete-betoncino” technology applied to both sides of the walls with galvanised steel, and the technology developed in CONSTRAIN. The detailed comparison is presented in this report and consists of the following.

Economic comparison

Considering the cost configuration that includes only materials and labour, the costs of using CONSTRAIN technology are lower (by 10.66% in the pilot case) than those of rete-betoncino technology.

Extending the cost configuration to include logistics costs, the need to relocate residents for the duration of the works – resulting from the rete-betoncino choice – makes the CONSTRAIN solution even more cost-effective.

Social and health consequences

CONSTRAIN technology involves the same inconveniences as any property maintenance; however, these can be mitigated by combining it with energy efficiency improvements, which tenants welcome due to the savings they provide.

The decision to use traditional technology and the resulting need to relocate occupants cause serious inconvenience for those affected, generating various forms of conflict and stress. Public housing companies must address these conflicts either by involving the occupants, which requires significant staff resources, or by meeting the costly requests of those relocated regarding the preparation of temporary premises.

At present, there is a lack of information on the psychological distress caused by relocation, especially among the elderly. However, international surveys highlight an increase in depression and other disorders.

In conclusion, the study has shown that:

- The ability of CONSTRAIN technology to significantly promote seismic risk reduction work on buildings is currently hampered by the very low willingness of people to undertake such work. This reluctance, evidenced by the modest use of substantial public funds allocated for this purpose, can largely be attributed to the considerable logistical and economic difficulties caused by the need to vacate the building for the duration of the work.
- The lower cost of applying CONSTRAIN technology compared to the traditional *rete-betoncino* technology.

Further analysis would be required to choose between seismic strengthening, and demolition and new construction; however, this is beyond the scope of this report.

3. Overview

This section, which aims to contextualise the project within the general framework of INTERREG ITALY SLOVENIA, is divided into the following points:

- Interreg ITA-SLO and topics addressed;
- CONSTRAIN objectives and results;
- Capitalisation call for proposals, PRO-SIS objectives and partnership characteristics;
- Study objectives.

The INTERREG ITALY-SLOVENIA V A 2014-2020 European territorial cooperation programme identified seismic risks among the environmental risks requiring attention. The inclusion of environmental safety in the cross-border cooperation programme, along with the observation that building safety measures in the Programme Area are extremely rare – despite large areas being characterised by high seismic risk – prompted the Department of Engineering and Architecture of the University of Trieste and the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Ljubljana to investigate the reasons for the lack of seismic risk reduction measures for buildings and possible solutions to the problem.

To this end, the two faculties promoted the CONSTRAIN project, in which the teams decided to involve four companies from the construction sector to facilitate the practical application of the knowledge to be acquired in the area.

The decision to expand the working group to include companies, in addition to facilitating the industrial application of theoretical research, responded to the request of the Interreg V A Programme, which, contributing to the implementation of the EU 2020 Strategy for Smart Growth, had included among its thematic objectives the technological transfer of research results to the productive sector and the strengthening of investments in applied research.

It is worth noting that seismic risk is defined as the probability that an earthquake will cause casualties and a certain level of destruction in a given area within a given period. This risk (R) is directly influenced by three variables: hazard (H), exposure (E), and vulnerability (V), and can be determined using the formula $R = H \times E \times V$.

The seismic hazard of an area cannot be modified by humans; it is determined by the proximity to continental plate collision points, which generate large amounts of energy when they come into contact. This energy, transmitted to the surface by seismic waves, causes earthquakes.

Exposure refers to the population density of an area and the economic, historical, and cultural value of the buildings located there. It is clear that this variable cannot be modified by socio-economic choices either.

Finally, vulnerability refers to the ability of structures to withstand an earthquake without suffering significant damage, and varies greatly depending on the materials used and the quality of construction. It is clear that this is the only variable that can be influenced by humans through initial construction choices and subsequent renovations.

As shown in detail later in this report, vulnerability is especially significant in Italy and Slovenia, as most of the building stock was constructed when building regulations did not exist or were inadequate, making it particularly susceptible in the event of seismic events.

A preliminary analysis of the reasons for the lack of seismic retrofitting of buildings showed that the main factors are:

- the high cost of interventions to prevent significant but uncertain damage;
- the logistical and social difficulties of relocating occupants during renovation or maintenance works.

The combination of these two factors has made seismic strengthening of existing buildings almost impossible.

In light of these premises, the CONSTRAIN project set out to define a technology that would require less costly interventions than those associated with traditional technologies and would not require the relocation of occupants. The strengthening should also raise the safety of masonry buildings to contemporary requirements.

The project team hypothesised that both causes of the failure to carry out safety measures could be overcome by acting only on the external part of the buildings, reinforced with composite materials.

Acting only on one side of the buildings offers further benefits:

- The use of materials and installation time is reduced, thereby lowering costs;
- If only the external part is involved, it is not necessary to move the occupants, thus avoiding the need and inconvenience of relocating them to a different location.

The results of the CONSTRAIN project² confirmed the validity of the initial solutions and made it possible to define optimised intervention strategies for the seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings. The effectiveness of the new technology was verified through an extensive significant experimental campaign.

As mentioned above, CONSTRAIN was an INTERREG ITALIA-SLOVENIJA project falling within the 2014-2020 European Programming.

The current programming period is 2021–2027. Below, the key points relating to the PRO-SIS project are outlined.

Each seven-year programme, including the current 2021-2027 programme, defines the priorities of the EU's Regional Policy, which aims to develop the various regions of the Union and, at the same time, eliminate income disparities and equalise opportunities among European citizens.

² A summary of the objectives and results of the CONSTRAIN project can be found <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>

The actions necessary to pursue these priorities are financed by resources allocated to the Structural Funds, in whose regulations they are included according to the function of each individual Fund³.

Furthermore, the regulations require that priorities be included in regional programmes and, ultimately, in the projects that will be funded.

European Territorial Cooperation (INTERREG) draws its financial resources from the ERDF structural fund⁴, for which, among other things⁵, the priority has been set: 'A more competitive and smarter Europe', which is broken down into the following specific objectives, subject to (partially binding) selection by the programmes benefiting from its resources:

- developing and strengthening research and innovation capacities and introducing advanced technologies;
- enabling citizens, businesses, research organisations and public authorities to benefit from digitalisation;
- strengthening sustainable growth and competitiveness of SMEs and creating jobs in SMEs, including through productive investment;
- developing skills for smart specialisation, industrial transition and entrepreneurship;
- strengthening digital connectivity;

One of the geographical areas funded by European territorial cooperation is the INTERREG VI A ITALIA SLOVENIJA Programme, which, within its scope of choice, has identified, among other things, "A more competitive and smarter Europe" as a priority, linking it to the specific objective of "developing and strengthening research and innovation capacities and the introduction of advanced technologies".

To achieve these strategic and specific objectives, the Italy-Slovenia programme document emphasises that: "the Programme will promote cooperation between R&D centres and businesses, facilitating technology transfer to SMEs, encouraging the creation of cross-border

³ Article 14 of Regulation (EU) 2021/1059 on European Territorial Cooperation INTERREG.

⁴ The ERDF (European Regional Development Fund), together with the ESF (European Social Fund) and the CF (Cohesion Fund), provides the resources for implementing EU regional policy.

⁵ There are five priorities for the Structural Funds for the 2021-2027 programming period, compared to eleven in the previous programming period.

These are:

- A more competitive and "smarter" Europe (ERDF priority)
- A "greener" and low-carbon Europe (ERDF and Cohesion Fund priority)
- A more connected Europe (Cohesion Fund priority)
- A more "social" and inclusive Europe (ESF+ priority)
- A Europe closer to its citizens

To these is added the specific priority for Territorial Cooperation programmes: Better governance of cooperation and A safer Europe.

networks and capitalising on R&D results in a new integrated framework that exploits the common priorities of S3⁶.

The same document also highlights the importance of capitalising on the projects that achieved the best results in the previous programme in order to produce tangible and measurable results: 'The projects to be funded are expected to achieve tangible and measurable results. To this end, the Programme will promote the implementation of joint pilot actions and the capitalisation of good practices from the previous INTERREG Italy-Slovenia Programme.'

A logical consequence of these last two points was the publication of the call for proposals on the capitalisation of projects funded by INTERREG V ITALY SLOVENIA 2014-2020⁷, which aimed to pursue objectives such as:

- Strengthen the impact and consolidate the outputs of the Interreg Italy-Slovenia 2014-2020 projects (FOLLOW-UP AND ENHANCEMENT OF OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLES);
- Provide better visibility of project outputs/deliverables (COMMUNICATION/VISIBILITY);
- Transferability and reuse of the outputs of Interreg Italy-Slovenia 2014-2020 projects to new partners within the programme area (TRANSFERABILITY/REUSE).

In response to this new call for proposals, and meeting the requirements, the Department of Engineering and Architecture of the University of Trieste and the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Ljubljana decided to prepare a project to capitalise on the knowledge acquired with CONSTRAIN. This new project, originating from CONSTRAIN and called PROSIS, was then awarded INTERREG funding.

The call for proposals, concerning the objective of "Transferability and reuse of the outputs of the Interreg Italy-Slovenia 2014-2020 projects to new partners within the programme area",

⁶ S3 – Smart Specialisation Strategy: starting with the 2014-2020 EU programming cycle for structural funds, the European Commission has promoted a new paradigm for supporting research and innovation, linking the use of ERDF resources to the adoption of a new strategic approach. The so-called ex-ante conditionality required all administrations responsible for Operational Programmes (national and regional) to define a "Smart Specialisation Strategy" (commonly referred to as S3), aimed at charting a path of economic transformation of the local production system towards market segments with higher added value and better prospects for competitive growth.

One of the cornerstones of this new strategic approach lies in the identification of a limited number of thematic priorities for support, identified following an in-depth analysis of the context and scenario and a targeted process of listening to the protagonists of local innovation dynamics, considering not only businesses and research organisations but also public administrations and civil society, as entities with a specific demand for innovation linked to social challenges.

The implementation of this new approach to programming required policy makers to set up an ad hoc monitoring and evaluation system to assess the extent to which the implementation of the programmes has created a framework for supporting research and innovation consistent with the choices made in terms of thematic priorities.

⁷ <https://www.ita-slo.eu/sites/default/files/media/document/01Capitalisation%20CallITASLOENG24-10-22F0.pdf>

introduced the need to support the project team with both output producers (Partner Givers) and users of the project outputs (Partner Takers). This led to an expansion of the team by including ATER Udine, for potential applications of CONSTRAIN technology on its social housing properties, and Zavod za varstvo kulturne dediščine Slovenije (Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia), to test the technology on buildings with historically and artistically significant façades. A company specialized in the production and marketing of innovative composite materials (FIBRE NET) and a research institute that conducts research, development and consulting in structures and infrastructures (Zavod za raziskavo materialov in konstrukcij - Slovenian for Institute for Research of Materials and Structures), completed the new team with their specific expertise in the construction sector.

As mentioned above, the CONSTRAIN project has developed strategies that enable significant reductions in seismic vulnerability through interventions carried out outside buildings. PROSIS aims to develop the tools necessary for the correct design and application of these strategies. In particular, accurate analytical and numerical algorithms are being developed and will be calibrated based on the experimental results of CONSTRAIN, in order to extend the range of cases studied experimentally and to provide professionals with tools for executive design, using the automatic calculation tools currently employed in their work.

The PRO-SIS project work plan, in WP 3, includes an analysis of the economic and social effects of using the identified strategies and an assessment of the economic impacts (direct, indirect and induced) of PRO-SIS measured according to the Input-Output model.

More specifically, Activity 3.5 – “Comparison of the costs of reinforcement interventions using the techniques developed in 'CONSTRAIN' with those of reinforcement interventions using currently used techniques” – aims to validate the economic effectiveness of the intervention techniques developed in “CONSTRAIN”. It involves conducting detailed cost analyses of interventions on pilot buildings, comparing reinforcement using ‘CONSTRAIN’ strategies with a conventional system involving reinforcement of the walls on both sides of the buildings. The result of these analyses is this report (Deliverable 3.5).

While researching the information needed to compile the report, it emerged that simply comparing the metric calculations in the two intervention scenarios would not be sufficient to communicate effectively the need to address seismic risk or to demonstrate that the technologies developed in CONSTRAIN and made accessible through the PROSIS outputs can significantly enhance safety, not only in the programme area but also in the rest of the two countries and beyond.

We have therefore gathered information that provides an initial estimate of:

- the overall scale of the problem and the legislative responses in place;
- the economic impact of the measures and the costs of not implementing them.

4. The overall scale of the problem: seismic risk

This part of the study addresses the question: are seismic risk reduction measures necessary in the programme area?

4.1. Seismic hazard in the programme area

The Mediterranean basin is subject to complex tectonic phenomena caused by the collision of the African and Eurasian plates. Although Europe and Africa are geographically separated by the Mediterranean Sea, this separation does not exist from a geological perspective. In this context, the two plates are in direct contact.

Specifically, the Programme Area corresponds to the northernmost part of the African plate, known as the Adria microplate (see Fig. 4.1).

Fig. 4.1 Adria microplate.

This microplate collides with and rotates counterclockwise relative to the Eurasian plate, sliding beneath it. This generates strong compressive forces that cause the subduction of the two rock plates.

The mechanical elasticity of the plates, resulting from the north-south convergent movement, leads to an accumulation of energy, which is released once the breaking point is reached, generating violent earthquakes in north-eastern Italy and western Slovenia, such as those in Friuli in 1976 and Bovec in 1998.

Fig. 4.2 shows a map of the seismic hazard in the area covering the territories of Interreg Italy-Slovenia and the surrounding regions.

Fig. 4.2 Seismic hazard (SHARE), PGA, 10% in 50 years.

Seismic hazard maps show the expected values of horizontal ground motion acceleration over a specified period and at a particular location. These maps present the expected accelerations for a homogeneous reference rock site. This seismic hazard map shows the horizontal acceleration for a vibration frequency of 5 hertz; the probability of this occurring for a building constructed on rock is 10% over fifty years (equivalent to once every 475 years). The data are based on the median of the European seismic hazard model SHARE.

The area's particular susceptibility to seismic activity has been documented historically since the Middle Ages, initially through written accounts produced in local towns and, in more recent times, through seismograph station readings.

Table 4.1 lists some of the main seismic events that have affected the area from 1300 to the present day. For the period between 1300 and 1976, only earthquakes that reached or exceeded a magnitude of 6.0 on the Richter scale are included; from 1977 onwards, events with a magnitude of 4.0 or greater are reported.

The greater detail for the latter period is due to the activation of a network of stations coordinated by the OGS Seismological Research Centre, which monitors earthquakes in north-eastern Italy and neighbouring areas.

Table 4.1 Main seismic events that have affected the project area from 1300 to the present day

Date	MW	Area or location of epicentre	Region
1348-01-25	6,6	Alpi Giulie	Alpi Giulie
1511-03-26	6,3	Friuli-Slovenia	Friuli-
1690-12-04	6,2	Villach	Carinzia
1695-02-25	6,4	Asolano	Veneto
1873-06-29	6,3	Alpago-Cansiglio	Veneto-
1895-04-14	6,1	Lubiana	Slovenia
1928-03-27	6,0	Carnia	Friuli
1936-10-18	6,1	Alpago-Cansiglio	Veneto-
1976-05-06	6,5	Friuli	Friuli
1977-09-16	5,68	Tolmezzo	Friuli
1979-04-18	5,12	Chiusaforte	Friuli
1980-10-14	4	Mel	Veneto
1983-02-10	4,28	Uccea	Friuli
1986-08-29	4	Mt. Pramaggiore	Friuli
1988-02-01	4,14	Tolmezzo	Friuli
1995-05-22	4	Ilirska Bistrica	Slovenia
1996-04-13	4,42	Claut	Friuli
1998-04-12	6,24	Bovec	Slovenia
1998-05-06	4,84	Kuk	Slovenia
1998-05-28	4,14	Trasaghis	Friuli
2002-02-14	5,26	Mt. Sernio	Friuli
2004-07-12	5,54	Bovec	Slovenia
2005-01-14	4,14	Podbrdo	Slovenia
2010-01-15	4	Postojna	Slovenia
2012-06-09	4,56	Barcis	Friuli
2014-04-22	4,98	Knezak	Slovenia
2015-01-30	4,14	Moggio Udinese	Friuli
2015-08-29	4,42	Bovec	Slovenia
2019-06-14	4	Verzegnis	Friuli
2020-07-17	4,28	Bovec	Slovenia
2024-03-27	4,1	Preone (UD)	Friuli
2024-12-09	5	Log nad Skofja Loko	Slovenia

The data were taken from 'Recent earthquakes (2000-2021) in the Friuli-Venezia Giulia region (north-eastern Italy) and surrounding areas and improvements in the quality of the OGS⁸ network's monitoring capabilities' and supplemented, for the years 2022-2025, with information downloadable from the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology's earthquake website⁹.

The information on earthquakes contained in the aforementioned publication or extracted from the INGV databases reported three variants of magnitude measurement scales: MW (moment magnitude), which takes into account the total energy released during an earthquake as a result of fault rupture and is more accurate for large magnitude events, MD (Duration Magnitude), which is measured by the duration of the seismogram, and ML (Local Magnitude), which is measured by the amplitude of the seismic waves recorded by a seismogram near the

⁸ In Bulletin of Geophysics and Oceanography Vol. 64, No. 3, pp. 237-258; September 2023

⁹ <https://terremoti.ingv.it/event/43185762>

epicentre of the event. To facilitate comparison between different seismic events, the data expressed in MD and ML have been converted to MW. The conversion was carried out according to the rules set out in the note¹⁰.

The seismic hazard of the programme area and neighbouring regions can be effectively illustrated with a topographical representation. In this context, Fig. 4.3¹¹ presents an image taken from the aforementioned publication, highlighting earthquakes with a magnitude Mw equal to or greater than 4.0 that occurred between 1000 and 5 May 1977.

The red dots indicate earthquakes with a magnitude Mw of 6.0 or greater, the orange dots highlight earthquakes with a magnitude of 5.0 or greater, and the yellow dots show those with a magnitude of 4.0 or greater.

Fig. 4.3 also shows the large number of faults located in this geographical area, many of which are considered particularly active and therefore dangerous.

The geographical references of earthquakes with a magnitude greater than or equal to 6.0, shown in red in Fig. 4.3, are listed in Table 4.2¹².

¹⁰ MI (local magnitude) is a measurement based on the amplitude of seismic waves recorded by a seismogram near the epicentre of the event.

Mw (moment magnitude) is a more global measurement that takes into account the total energy released during an earthquake, and is more accurate for large magnitude events.

A commonly used conversion formula, albeit approximate, for converting from MI to Mw is as follows:
 $Mw = ML + 0.9$

However, this formula is sufficiently accurate for earthquakes with a local magnitude of MI between 3 and 7 and for events not too far from the recording point. For very large or very small events, the relationship may vary significantly, so in these cases it is best to refer to specific seismological studies.

The Md magnitude, the third measurement scale mentioned in the publication, is measured by the duration of the seismogram. The basic concept is that the greater the magnitude of an event, the longer the duration of the recording. As it is very simple and straightforward to measure the duration of the seismogram, since 1980, the duration magnitude has been included among the parameters provided to the Civil Protection Agency. The others are the location of the event and its theoretical intensity.

In this case too, it is possible, albeit approximately, to convert the magnitude of an earthquake from Md (magnitude duration) to Mw (moment magnitude).

The relationship between Md and Mw is not always direct, but there are empirical formulas that can be used to make this conversion. One of the most common relationships is as follows:

$$Mw = Md + (0.4 \times (Md - 4.0))$$

This formula is valid for earthquakes with a magnitude Md greater than approximately 4.0. Of course, the conversion may not be perfect for very small or very large earthquakes, but generally this relationship provides a fairly accurate estimate.

¹¹ Recent earthquakes (2000–2021) in the Friuli-Venezia Giulia region (north-eastern Italy) and surrounding areas, and improvements in the quality of the OGS network's monitoring capabilities

¹² The 1895 Ljubljana earthquake, despite having a magnitude of 6.1, is not reported as it occurred outside the survey area

Fig. 4.3 Seismic hazard (SHARE), PGA, 10% in 50 years.

Table 4.2 Main earthquakes in Friuli-Venezia Giulia, between 1000 and 1977.

No.	Year	Mo	Da	Ho	Mi	Epicentral Area	Lat. N (°)	Lon. E (°)	I_0 (MCS)	M_w
1	1348	01	25			Julian Alps	46.504	13.581	9	6.6
2	1511	03	26	15	30	Friuli-Slovenia	46.209	13.216	9	6.3
3	1690	12	04	14		Villach, Carinthia	46.633	13.880	8-9	6.2
4	1695	02	25	05	30	Asolano	45.861	11.910	10	6.4
5	1873	06	29	03	58	Alpago-Cansiglio	46.159	12.383	9-10	6.3
6	1928	03	27	08	32	Carnia	46.372	12.975	9	6.0
7	1936	10	18	03	10	Alpago-Cansiglio	46.089	12.380	9	6.1
8	1976	05	06	20	00	Friuli	46.262	13.279	9-10	6.5

The area to be considered must be divided into sub-areas defined according to their seismic hazard. Fig. 4.4 is a map of Friuli-Venezia Giulia divided into the three seismic hazard zones. Fig. 4.5 is a map of Veneto municipality and Fig. 4.6 is that of Slovenia. The risk, assessed on the basis of maximum ground acceleration, is highest in zone 1¹³ and gradually decreases in zones 2 and 3. The province of Venice, the only part of the region included in the programme area, has the lowest level of seismic hazard.

The information on seismic hazard in Slovenia, highlights the presence of a large area that falls within the highest seismic hazard category, a significant part of which is included in the Interreg ITA-SLO area.

¹³ Maximum horizontal acceleration on flat, rigid ground is conventionally defined as the maximum horizontal acceleration on flat, rigid ground, which has a 10% probability of being exceeded in a 50-year period.

In summary, the Programme Area, excluding only the coastal areas, is located in a zone of high or medium seismic risk, which explains the need to intervene according to criteria of effectiveness and efficiency, with the latter understood as cost-effectiveness.

Fig. 4.4 Seismic classification of Friuli-Venezia Giulia Region (Source: Friuli-Venezia Giulia Region).

Fig. 4.5 Seismic classification of Veneto Region (Source: Veneto Region).

Fig. 4.6 Seismic classification of Slovenia (Source: Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Slovenia, Administration of the Republic of Slovenia for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief)¹⁴.

¹⁴ The European Macroseismic Scale (EMS) is a 12-point scale:

VI – Earthquake causing minor damage, but frightening many people who run outdoors. Some objects fall to the ground. Many buildings suffer minor non-structural damage (small cracks in plaster, small pieces of plaster falling).

VII – Earthquake causing moderate damage: most people are frightened and run outside. Stable furniture is moved from its position and objects fall from shelves. Numerous well-built buildings suffer moderate damage, such as small cracks in walls and small pieces of plaster or chimneys falling. In older buildings, cracks may appear in walls or partition walls may collapse.

4.2. Exposure of the programme area and comparisons with national data

The second factor to consider when assessing the seismic risk of a given geographical area is exposure. Its degree is determined by the population density in the area under assessment and by the economic, historical, artistic, and cultural value of the buildings located there. Below, using available statistical sources, these variables are examined, focusing on those relating to Friuli-Venezia Giulia. It should be noted that the available data are not always comprehensive and, in some cases, lack the level of detail required for the purposes of this study.

4.2.1. Population density

The average population density in Friuli-Venezia Giulia is 151 inhabitants per km². Although this is lower than the Italian average of 195.3 inhabitants per km², it ranks in the middle range of Italian regions (Fig. 4.7) and is well above the EU-27 average of 106.3 inhabitants per km². In 2022 the average population density of Slovenia was 104.8 inhabitants per km², while that of the Programme Area is approximately 150 inhabitants per km², influenced – as shown in Table 6 – by significant variations across the different areas, divided at NUTS 3 level¹⁵.

DENSITÀ DELLA POPOLAZIONE DEI COMUNI. ANNO 2023 (ABITANTI PER KMQ)

Fig. 4.7 ISTAT Movement and calculation of the annual resident population

If the population density in the three risk areas of Friuli-Venezia Giulia (see Appendix) is considered (Table 4.3), it is observed that zone 1, which has the highest risk, fortunately has a much lower population density than the other two zones. Specifically, zone 1 – where only 75,485 people out of a regional total of 1,194,616 resided on 1 January 2024 – has an average density of 59 inhabitants per km², while zone 3, which has the lowest risk, has an average density of 231 inhabitants per km². In percentage terms, zone 3 contains the highest proportion of the regional population (47.24%), compared to 6.32% in zone 1 (Table 4.4).

VIII – Earthquake with serious consequences: people have difficulty maintaining their balance. Large cracks form in the walls of many buildings. Walls may collapse in individual well-constructed buildings, while poorly constructed buildings may collapse completely.

* The effects of the earthquake may be intensified in areas with less favourable geological conditions, on steeper slopes or in areas with a high level of groundwater.

¹⁵ The European Union is divided into NUTS 1, 2 and 3 statistical zones. Zone 1 corresponds to countries, zone 2 to regions and zone 3 to provinces or equivalent political entities.

Table 4.3 ISTAT data

	Population	Area KM2	Density
Area 3	564.356	2439	231
Area 2	554.775	4.214	132
Area 1	75.485	1.280	59
Total	1.194.616	7.933	151

Table 4.4 Calculations based on ISTAT data

	Population %	Surface KM2 %
Area 3	47,24	31
Area 2	46,44	53
Area 1	6,32	16
Total	100	100

Information on the inhabitants, surface area and population density of the municipalities of Friuli-Venezia Giulia, broken down by seismic zone, is provided in the Appendix.

Due to the significant variance in population density, it is interesting to observe how it is distributed in the Programme Area when divided at the NUTS 3 level¹⁶.

Table 4.5 Population density distribution in the Programme Area divided at NUTS 3 level (Source: EUROSTAT)

TIME		2023
GEO (Codes)	GEO (Labels)	
ITH35	Venezia	433,2
ITH41	Pordenone	139,8
ITH42	Udine	108,8
ITH43	Gorizia	361,7
ITH44	Trieste	1.073,0
SI038	Primorsko-notranjska	37,6
SI041	Osrednjeslovenska	242,0
SI042	Gorenjska	98,8
SI043	Goriška	51,1
SI044	Obalno-kraška	114,2

Fig. 4.8 provides an overview of population density in the Programme Area. When superimposed on Fig. 4.6, it clearly shows that the area with the highest seismic risk in the Slovenian NUTS 3 regions is characterised by low population density.

¹⁶ The NUTS 3 level takes into account the territory of the EU divided into provinces or statistical districts

Fig. 4.8 Overview of the population density in the Programme Area, divided at NUTS 3 level.

4.2.2. Economic value of buildings

The second factor in assessing a territory's exposure to seismic risk is the economic value of the buildings located there. The source normally used to quantify the value of properties in Italy is the Revenue Agency. The Agency's estimates take into account both the category and cadastral income, as well as the market value of the area in which the property is located¹⁷. Nevertheless, outdated cadastral classifications (reference census period 1988/89) and the failure to take urban development into account have led to distortions in the representativeness of income in relation to the characteristics of properties and therefore their overall value.

Added to this is illegal building, which in some regions has a very significant impact (Fig. 4.9) and ultimately leads to a considerable underestimation of the value of the national property portfolio. However, focusing on Friuli-Venezia Giulia, which is a significant part of this study, although it is known that the properties values are underestimated, illegal construction has minimal relevance in this context. The Agency's data are much more representative of reality than those of many Italian regions and, despite the critical issues, the Agency's estimate remains the best available for assessing the entire housing stock.

The Revenue Agency reports its estimates for the entire national territory, as well as by macro areas, which are further divided by individual regions.

¹⁷ The procedure used by the Revenue Agency to assign value to properties is very complex. It is explained in the methodological note (Chapter 7) of the Publication, in this case "Properties in Italy 2023". Below is the link to the methodological note.

https://www.agenziaentrate.gov.it/portale/documents/20143/5327584/Gli+immobili+in+Italia_2023_cap_7.pdf/eadd7488-c1af-ddee-5603-8c699e365378?t=1685524400553

Fig. 4.9 Index of illegal construction in Italy.

Below are reported:

- the estimated asset value of dwellings owned by individuals (PF) and other entities (PNF: legal entities, etc.), taken from 'Real Estate in Italy 2023'¹⁸;
- estimates of the asset value of properties intended for non-residential. The latter, regarding the national stock, are taken from the '2025 Real Estate Report'.

Data on surface areas are based on the cadastral statistics tables - available in Excel (xls) format at provincial level at the link provided in the note¹⁹ - and, for the market prices of the different types of assets, on the information contained in the aforementioned 'Real Estate Report 2025'.

Estimation of the asset value of residential houses

Table 4.6 shows that in 2020, real estate assets intended for residential use in Friuli-Venezia Giulia amounted to approximately €108.4 billion.

It would be useful to know the value of real estate in Friuli-Venezia Giulia broken down by seismic zone. Although this information can be obtained from the same source, it has not been extrapolated at this time. The attempt is to provide herein a specific assessment, based on cross-referencing data and estimates from various sources, in the section on vulnerability. It is believed that it is possible to determine the value of real estate by seismic zone is based on the

¹⁸ <https://www.agenziaentrate.gov.it/portale/gli-immobili-in-italia-2023>

¹⁹ <https://www.agenziaentrate.gov.it/portale/schede/fabbricatiterreni/omi/pubblicazioni/statistiche-catastali>

fact that CRESME²⁰ has broken down property values by climate zone, and therefore the same association also be possible for seismic zones.

Appendix 2 shows the association between climate zones and seismic zones for all municipalities in the FVG region, serving as a starting point for extracting the required data. Note that there is no exact correspondence between the national table of climate zones and that of seismic zones for municipalities. For example, in the climate zone table, Sappada is still listed in Veneto, and the amalgamation of municipalities is not considered.

Table 4.6 Estimation of the asset value of dwellings in Italy 2023, relative to 2020, data in billions of euros (Source: Italian Revenue Agency).

Tabella 2.2 – Stima del valore patrimoniale (VSM) delle abitazioni e delle pertinenze (PF e PNF) – Dati regionali

anno 2020 Area territoriale	Regione	VSM abitazioni (mld €) PF	Quota % PF	VSM abitazioni (mld €) PNF	Quota % PNF	VSM pertinenze (mld €) PF	Quota % PF	VSM pertinenze (mld €) PNF	Quota % PNF
Nord Ovest	Liguria	225,1	94,2%	13,8	5,8%	13,9	89,5%	1,6	10,5%
	Lombardia	861,9	90,8%	87,5	9,2%	73,9	88,2%	9,9	11,8%
	Piemonte	328,2	93,1%	24,1	6,9%	24,6	91,5%	2,3	8,5%
	Valle d'Aosta	24,0	93,0%	1,8	7,0%	2,2	89,1%	0,3	10,9%
Nord Ovest Totale		1.439,2	91,9%	127,2	8,1%	114,5	89,1%	14,1	10,9%
Nord Est	Emilia-Romagna	399,4	93,9%	25,8	6,1%	33,9	92,4%	2,8	7,6%
	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	95,0	93,5%	6,6	6,5%	6,2	90,7%	0,6	9,3%
	Trentino-Alto Adige	176,8	90,9%	17,8	9,1%	12,1	85,7%	2,0	14,3%
	Veneto	443,8	93,8%	29,2	6,2%	34,7	91,8%	3,1	8,2%
Nord Est Totale		1.115,0	93,4%	79,4	6,6%	86,8	91,1%	8,5	8,9%
Centro	Lazio	606,5	90,2%	66,0	9,8%	31,2	85,1%	5,5	14,9%
	Marche	121,4	95,6%	5,6	4,4%	8,0	94,0%	0,5	6,0%
	Toscana	412,1	93,2%	30,1	6,8%	22,1	92,5%	1,8	7,5%
	Umbria	62,2	94,3%	3,7	5,7%	4,5	92,9%	0,3	7,1%
Centro Totale		1.202,2	91,9%	105,5	8,1%	65,8	89,0%	8,1	11,0%
Sud	Abruzzo	91,3	94,7%	5,1	5,3%	5,3	92,5%	0,4	7,5%
	Basilicata	27,5	94,3%	1,7	5,7%	1,5	92,9%	0,1	7,1%
	Calabria	99,3	94,7%	5,6	5,3%	2,4	92,2%	0,2	7,8%
	Campania	411,5	93,0%	30,8	7,0%	13,2	88,6%	1,7	11,4%
	Molise	17,2	95,3%	0,8	4,7%	1,1	93,8%	0,1	6,2%
	Puglia	251,7	95,0%	13,2	5,0%	12,4	92,4%	1,0	7,6%
Sud Totale		898,5	94,0%	57,2	6,0%	35,9	91,0%	3,5	9,0%
Isole	Sardegna	147,1	92,9%	11,2	7,1%	4,0	85,2%	0,7	14,8%
	Sicilia	298,1	95,6%	13,6	4,4%	10,3	94,3%	0,6	5,7%
Isole Totale		445,1	94,7%	24,8	5,3%	14,3	91,6%	1,3	8,4%

²⁰ CRESME Centre for Economic, Sociological and Market Research for the Construction Industry

Estimation of the asset value of properties used for non-residential

To maintain consistency in the values, only the stock of offices, shops and workshops is considered. The evaluation of these categories is facilitated by recording prices for each individual Italian municipality in the property price database²¹ of the Revenue Agency. Their six-monthly update ensures that the estimate corresponds to the actual value of the property units.

While maintaining a good level of information, the impossibility - due to a lack of data - of estimating all property categories will result in an underestimation of the regional assets. Examples of properties not included in the estimate, taken from ENEA's "La consistenza del parco immobiliare italiano 2024" (The size of the Italian property portfolio in 2024), are given in the note²². In addition, industrial warehouses are excluded, for the reasons explained at the end of this paragraph. Table 4.7 shows the 2024 stock of "non-residential property units" taken from the 2025 Real Estate Report by the OMI Revenue Agency.

RAPPORTO IMMOBILIARE 2025
Immobili a destinazione terziaria, commerciale e produttiva

OSSEVATORIO DEL MERCATO IMMOBILIARE

Stock	Terziario - Commerciale (TCO)							Produttivo (PRO) D/1 e D/7	Produttivo agricolo (AGR) D/10	Totale
	Uffici A/10	Negozi e laboratori C/1 e C/3	Depositi comm. e autorimesse	Uffici pubblici B/4	Istituti di credito D/5	Edifici comm. D/8	Alberghi D/2			
Nord Ovest	188.349	597.408	1.253.297	12.504	5.904	77.249	13.525	264.733	97.519	2.510.488
Nord Est	141.635	387.876	755.175	8.715	4.266	53.983	13.915	216.007	144.441	1.726.013
Centro	129.559	546.292	998.060	8.212	3.469	46.106	14.030	146.812	72.757	1.965.297
Sud	112.815	680.695	1.519.227	9.715	2.214	56.505	12.337	144.396	60.539	2.598.443
Isole	53.634	283.280	667.895	6.561	1.273	18.792	6.457	58.923	48.520	1.145.335
ITALIA	625.992	2.495.551	5.193.654	45.707	17.126	252.635	60.264	830.871	423.776	9.945.576

Table 4.7 Commercial and service-sector real estate in Italy (Source: OMI Revenue Agency Real Estate Report 2025)

²¹ <https://www1.agenziaentrate.gov.it/servizi/Consultazione/ricerca.htm?level=0>

Tabella 39. Numero e distribuzione nazionale delle strutture sanitarie pubbliche nel 2021 [4]

Regione	Assistenza Ospedaliera	Ambulatori e Laboratori	Altri Tipi di Strutture Territoriali	Strutture Semiresidenziali	Strutture Residenziali	Istituti di riabilitazione	Totale
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	10	55	140	42	87	0	334

Tabella 86. Ripartizione del numero di strutture museali pubbliche e private per Regione [7]

Regione	Totali	Totali escluse le aree archeologiche prive di strutture museali	Pubbliche escluse le aree archeologiche prive di strutture museali	Private escluse le aree archeologiche prive di strutture museali
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	145	139	96	43

Tabella 87. Ripartizione del numero di biblioteche pubbliche e private per Regione [7]

Regione	Strutture totali	Pubbliche	Private
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	268	225	43

Of the commercial service sectors, mentioned above, only categories A10 (Offices) and C1, C3 (Shops and Workshops) are considered. For the manufacturing sector - categories D1 (Factories) and D7 (Buildings for Specific Industrial Needs) - the Agency reports only the value per square metre (Table 4.13 and Table 4.14). However, as there is no data on surface area, it is not possible to assess the total asset value of these categories.

Table 4.8 Ordinary use properties: category A10 in Friuli-Venezia Giulia: offices and private practices (Source: Real Estate Market Observatory, Revenue Agency)

Area	Region	Province	N° U.I.U. ²³	Total cadastral income	Total number of rooms	Total estimated surface area in m2
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	GORIZIA	1.536	2.153.564	7.180	175.597
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	PORDENONE	3.609	5.775.028	18.617	494.056
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	TRIESTE	2.638	8.518.550	16.760	448.007
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	UDINE	7.025	12.247.607	36.597	962.233
Total			14.808			2.079.893

Table 4.9 Ordinary use properties: category A10 in North-East of Italy: offices and private practices (Source: Real Estate Market Observatory, Revenue Agency)

Tabella 11: Quotazione media, variazione annua e indice territoriale per area geografica e per regione – Uffici

Area	Regione	Quotazione media Uffici 2024 (€/m ²)	Var. % quotazione 2024/2023	Indice territoriale
Nord Est	Emilia-Romagna	1.366	-0,8%	103,8
	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	903	0,1%	68,6
	Veneto	1.348	0,4%	102,4

Taking the estimated surface area from Table 4.9 (2,079,893 m²) and the average price from Table 4.6 (€903 per m²), the total value of the offices in Friuli-Venezia Giulia is €1,878,143,379. Considering the asset value of shops and laboratories in Friuli-Venezia Giulia, and noting that the Agency indicates the same market price per m²:

²³ An urban real estate unit (UIU) is a portion of a building, an entire building or a group of buildings which, in its current state, is capable of generating independent income. Urban real estate units (UIU) corresponding to portions of buildings are, for example, flats, shops or garages which, although not occupying an entire building, can generate their own income. Examples of UIUs represented by entire buildings are villas, cottages, schools and hotels. Finally, UIUs consisting of a group of buildings are, for example, factories and hospitals.

Table 4.10 SHOPS C1 (Source: Real Estate Market Observatory, Revenue Agency)

Area	Region	Province	N° U.I.U.	Total cadastral income	Total estimated surface area in m2
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	GORIZIA	4.902	6.998.071	374.310
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	PORDENONE	7.491	16.404.035	735.513
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	TRIESTE	7.289	10.165.830	487.313
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	UDINE	15.289	25.579.546	1.413.930
TOTALI			34.971	59.147.482	3.011.066

Table 4.11 LABORATORIES C3 (Source: Real Estate Market Observatory, Revenue Agency)

Area	Region	Province	N° U.I.U.	Total cadastral income	Total estimated surface area in m2
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	GORIZIA	436	109.263	46.511
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	PORDENONE	1.969	877.095	384.664
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	TRIESTE	906	446.191	103.748
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	UDINE	3.664	1.376.665	579.767
TOTALI			6.975	2.809.214	1.114.690

Table 4.12 Shops and laboratories in North-East of Italy (Source: OMI Revenue Agency Real Estate Report 2025)

Area	Regione	Quotazione media Negozi 2024 (€/m ²)	Var % quotazione 2024/2023	Indice territoriale
Nord Est	Emilia-Romagna	1.490	-2,0%	104,8
	Friuli Venezia Giulia	1.171	-0,1%	82,4
	Veneto	1.625	1,8%	114,3
	Nord Est	1.535	0,0%	107,9

Table 4.13 FACTORIES D1 (Source: Real Estate Market Observatory, Revenue Agency)

Area	Region	province abbreviation	Province	N° U.I.U. with income	Total cadastral income
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	GO	GORIZIA	1.097	5.359.342
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	PN	PORDENONE	3.730	19.556.054
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	TS	TRIESTE	958	3.665.169
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	UD	UDINE	5.536	10.475.131

Table 4.14 BUILDINGS CONSTRUCTED FOR INDUSTRIAL PURPOSES D7 (Source: Real Estate Market Observatory, Revenue Agency)

Area	Region	province abbreviation	Province	N° U.I.U. with income	Total cadastral income
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	GO	GORIZIA	1.057	8.109.518
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	PN	PORDENONE	2.762	28.644.081
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	TS	TRIESTE	714	9.543.707
NORD-EST	FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA	UD	UDINE	6.449	46.145.220

Table 4.15 Factories and 10 buildings constructed for industrial purposes in North-East of Italy (Source: OMI Revenue Agency Real Estate Report 2025)

Area	Regione	Quotazione media Capannoni 2024 (€/m ²)	Var % quotazione 2024/2023	Indice territoriale
Nord Est	Emilia-Romagna	459	0,6%	102,5
	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	296	0,0%	66,1
	Veneto	470	0,2%	104,9
Nord Est		451	0,4%	100,7

Given the lack of information on the value of non-residential assets, it is believed that summing the identified values has any economic significance.

It may be useful to correlate the seismic risk exposure of industrial activities with the number of companies present in the area. The greater the number of employees, the more advanced the technologies used, and the higher the exposure, both in terms of the concentration of personnel and capital. To provide an immediate indication of the risk exposure of production activities, the seismic hazard map could be superimposed on the distribution of companies throughout Italy (Table 4.14).

It would be observed that in Northern Italy, classified as seismic-prone more recently, the industrial building stock is less adequate in terms of seismic requirements. Exposure to risk is also greatest in a strip extending from the northern Adriatic coast along the Emilian Apennines, involving northern Lombardy and reaching the Triveneto region.

Since seismic risk is defined as the product of seismic hazard, vulnerability, and exposure, it is clear that the northern Apennine area, along with the north-eastern part of Italy, are the areas where this risk for industrial structures is greatest.

Fig. 4.10 Distribution by density of businesses in the Italian territory

4.2.3. Considerations on cultural heritage

The final element to consider for exposure – and also the most difficult to assess – is the value of the area's historical, artistic, and cultural heritage. While it is almost never possible to quantify this financially, it is at least possible to quantify it numerically by type and to define its significance within the national context. The logic underlying quantitative research assumes that exposure increases with a greater presence of cultural heritage in the area, and that this exposure is further affected by the location of assets within various hazard zones. In this analysis, the need is essentially to determine whether Friuli-Venezia Giulia possesses significant artistic and cultural heritage and how it is distributed with respect to seismic zoning.

Initial objective information on the value of a country or region's cultural heritage can be found in the UNESCO World Heritage List. ISTAT uses this list as a starting point in its annual report "BES Benessere Equo e Solidale" (Fair and Solidarity Well-being) to identify the "Density of cultural heritage (archaeological, architectural, and museum assets, also weighted according to their attractiveness), in relation to the resident population by region."

According to the 2023 report, Fig. 4.11 shows the top 20 countries by number of heritage listings and the distribution of Italian heritage across various regions. Italy ranks as the world's leading country, with the Friuli-Venezia Giulia region in ninth place. This provides an initial indication of the region's cultural heritage.

Fig. 4.11 Properties listed on the UNESCO World Heritage List by category and country/region. Year 2023 (Source: ISTAT)

Further confirmation comes from the same publication, which, in its 2013 report, provides useful information illustrating the density of heritage in relation to the area where it is distributed and the population residing there.

xxx

The information in Fig. 4.12 correlates population density with the density of registered assets per 100 km². Friuli-Venezia Giulia, which has an average density of 151 inhabitants per km², has a relatively high number of registered assets.

A logical consequence of the values highlighted in the chart is that regions with a high density of assets and a relatively low population density are better positioned to protect and enhance their cultural heritage as a factor in social well-being, while also benefiting from contextual conditions that are generally more favourable to heritage preservation. In this respect, one of the advantaged regions is Friuli-Venezia Giulia.

Fig. 4.12 Correlation between population density and density of registered assets.

Regarding the census of cultural assets and their risk, the Ministry of Culture provides the “VINCOLI in rete” system (Fig. 4.13), which uses various databases for their census and cataloguing. One of these, the “Carta del Rischio” (Risk chart), provides information for assessing their condition.

Fig. 4.13 The “VINCOLI in rete” webpage layout

From the STATISTICS/DOCUMENTATION of VINCOLI online, the quantity of assets at risk, including those at seismic risk, present in Italy are obtained. At the end of 2021, almost 110,000 assets were registered in the Cultural Heritage Risk Map (currently, many more); unfortunately, over 50,000 were abandoned or unusable. ISTAT estimated that, in 2016, nearly 60% of public buildings (valued at approximately €340 billion) were severely underused, lacking economic, social, or cultural viability.

Another database in the VINCOLI in rete system is the SIGECweb portal, which contains the cataloguing and descriptions of a significant number of assets. The portal is regularly updated with new entries.

A breakdown of the assets catalogued in the VINCOLI in rete system is provided in Fig. 4.14²⁴. For the Friuli-Venezia Giulia region, VINCOLI in rete contains more than 7,500 files (Fig. 4.15) divided into the following categories: Architecture (the largest); Archaeological complexes; Archaeological monuments; Parks/gardens; Archaeological sites; UNESCO sites.

Fig. 4.14 Summary of the Italian assets listed in the VINCOLI in rete webpage

²⁴ SIGECweb, an acronym for Sistema Informativo Generale del Catalogo sul Web (General Information System for the Web Catalogue), is a digital platform developed by the Central Institute for Cataloguing and Documentation (ICCD) for the cataloging of cultural heritage in Italy. It manages the entire cataloging process, from the production and dissemination of cataloging standards to the assignment of unique codes, and the management and sharing of data with other systems.

SISTEMA VINCOLI IN RETE: REGIONE FRIULI-VENEZIA GIULIA: TOTALE DEI BENI SUDDIVISI PER TIPO SCHEDA

Tipo scheda	Totale
Architettura	7344
Complessi archeologici	14
Monumenti archeologici	186
Parchi/giardini	31
Siti archeologici	34
Siti Unesco	1

Fig. 4.15 Summary of the assets listed in the VINCOLI in rete webpage, for the Friuli-Venezia Giulia region

The aspects most directly relevant to understanding the risks, including seismic risks, to which Italian heritage is exposed are reported in the aforementioned Risk Map. The Map is an extremely important territorial information tool for understanding the natural risks to which Italian artistic and archaeological heritage, both protected and unprotected, is exposed. Its management was originally assigned to the General Directorate for the Security of Cultural Heritage²⁵ with responsibility for safety, both in "ordinary" situations²⁶ (fire safety, human safety, seismic risk prevention) and in emergency situations. The Directorate was abolished in November 2025 and its functions were transferred to the Department for the Protection of Cultural Heritage (DiT). Its web pages, where guidelines for compiling technical data sheets relating to the risks of various types of artistic and cultural heritage assets can be downloaded, remain active²⁷.

The Risk Map Territorial Information System provides public access to online data. To log in with a public profile, use the username "pubblico" and the password "pubblico". The link is provided in the footnote²⁸. The site allows you to view the area map showing property locations,

²⁵ Risk analysis and study are carried out by the Directorate in collaboration with many bodies responsible for understanding and protecting the territory, including: the Civil Protection Department of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, the Carabinieri Cultural Heritage Protection Unit, the Higher Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA), and the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology (INGV).

²⁶ Below are the government provisions aimed at minimizing damage to cultural heritage with respect to "Immediate damage: reduction of vulnerabilities - prevention measures"

- Directive of the President of the Council of Ministers of February 9, 2011, "Guidelines for the assessment and reduction of seismic risk of cultural heritage with reference to the new Technical Standards for construction pursuant to the decree of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport of January 14, 2008" (ordinary supplement to the Official Journal of February 26, 2011)

- Circular of the Secretary General no. 15 of April 30, 2015

- Cataloguing

- Territorial Risk Map System

²⁷ <https://dgspatrimonioculturale.beniculturali.it/attivita-direzione-generale-sicurezza-del-patrimonio-culturale/il-sistema-informativo-della-carta-del-rischio/>

²⁸ <http://www.cartadelrischio.beniculturali.it/>

data on territorial hazards, and seismic vulnerability and risk. The data sheets give a detailed overview of the current situation in Italy, although the incomplete technical survey of many properties indicates that much remains to be done.

The two images below (Fig. 4.16 and Fig. 4.17) show properties at risk from seismic activity in the municipality of Grado. Specifically, two churches, marked by the red triangle, are considered to be at high seismic risk. In this case, the hazard is clearly linked to vulnerability, as Grado is in the lowest seismic hazard zone. This example illustrates that seismic risk reduction measures should not be limited to areas with the highest hazard.

Fig. 4.16 Example of the properties at risk of seismic activity located in the municipality of Grado: global view

Fig. 4.17 Example of the properties at risk of seismic activity located in the municipality of Grado: detail of the historical city centre

Regarding cultural heritage exposed to seismic risk, another contribution comes from ISPRA²⁹ which, based on data from Vincoli in Rete, within the framework of content developed for the National System for Environmental Protection, highlights among various indicators the assets exposed to risk divided by seismic hazard area. ISPRA data, as of 31 December, 2024, show that 16,729 assets are located in municipalities classified as areas where the probability of a strong earthquake is high (Class 1), equal to 7.3% of the total. Overall, the assets located in municipalities in seismic class 1 or 2 number 109,346. A summary is shown in Fig. 4.18³⁰. Regarding regional data, Friuli-Venezia Giulia has 3,558 cultural properties in seismic zone 1 or 2.

Again, according to ISPRA's calculations, three municipalities within the INTERREG Italy-Slovenia and Italy-Austria programme areas are among the top twenty Italian municipalities with the highest number of cultural assets exposed to high seismic risk (Table 4.16).

Region	Municipalities in seismic class 1 and 2	Cultural heritage
Piemonte	-	-
Valle D'Aosta	-	-
Lombardia	57	2.033
Trentino-AA	3	37
Veneto	257	11.800
Friuli-VeneziaG	135	3.558
Liguria	41	1.990
Emilia-Romagna	109	5.893
Toscana	89	4.292
Umbria	74	6.315
Marche	225	22.885
Lazio	274	12.139
Abruzzo	265	4.536
Molise	127	5.325
Campania	445	11.331
Puglia	67	1.932
Basilicata	124	2.255
Calabria	370	5.119
Sicilia	336	7.906
Sardegna	-	-
TOTAL	2.998	109.346

Fig. 4.18 ISPRA Italian map of cultural heritage assets exposed to seismic risk

Table 4.16 Italian municipalities with higher number of cultural heritage assets exposed to seismic risk (Source: ISPRA)

²⁹ Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Institute for Environmental Protection and Research

³⁰ <https://indicatoriambientali.isprambiente.it/it/pericolosita-sismica/beni-culturali-esposti-pericolosita-sismica>

Municipality	N. Cultural heritage
L'Aquila	714
Messina	422
Spoletto	419
Foligno	353
Reggio di Calabria	328
Benevento	320
Siracusa	298
Sulmona	280
Vittorio Veneto	268
Visso	258
Belluno	254
Arquata del Tronto	210
Cosenza	188
Ragusa	168
Noto	166
Pieve Torina	160
Venzone	157
Isernia	151
Vibo Valentia	140
Modica	129

4.3. Vulnerability of real estate in the program area

Seismic vulnerability indicates how susceptible a building is to damage during an earthquake. Of the three variables that determine seismic risk, it is the only one that can be changed by actions.

Attention to the seismic vulnerability of real estate should be particularly important in both Italy and the Program Area, regions characterised by many high-risk zones. One such area is the south-eastern Alps, which includes Friuli and extends, near the political border, to Slovenia and Carinthia. In this area, potentially destructive earthquakes have a return period of approximately 20–30 years³¹.

The degree of vulnerability of a property is determined by many factors, such as construction techniques and materials used, maintenance, site location, and others. Among these, construction techniques are particularly important, as they depend on the regulations in force in the area at the time of construction. Therefore, for an initial assessment³² of the degree of

³¹ <https://www.protezionecivile.fvg.it/getDoc.php?file=11285.pdf>

³² This report does not aim to delve into the vulnerability of an area's buildings using the models proposed by scholars in recent decades.

vulnerability³³ of the real estate assets in a territory, one must start from its seismic zoning³⁴ or from the destructive seismic events it has experienced, and then link the building regulations to them as they evolve over time.

4.3.1. Evolution of Italian seismic regulations

In Italy, the first seismic legislation, which also included the identification of seismic zones, was Royal Decree No. 193 of 1909, issued following the destructive earthquakes in Reggio Calabria and Messina in 1908. The areas subject to the application of the technical standards contained in this decree were limited to the provinces of Catanzaro, Reggio Calabria, and Messina (Fig. 4.19). Consequently, in almost all of the country, there was no obligation to build in accordance with seismic regulations.

³³ For a future study on the vulnerability of the regional real estate assets, and more specifically on that of the regional ATERs, it is interesting to report the considerations contained in the update of the PRGRU guidelines of the Campania Region (2024).

15.3.8 Vulnerability Assessment of Buildings, Infrastructure, and Architectural Assets

The following are some useful considerations for initiating or implementing studies on the seismic vulnerability of assets, which could provide useful data for rapidly quantifying the debris and materials resulting from collapse and demolition after an earthquake.

The assessment should be based, as already mentioned, on the probability of a seismic event occurring and on the vulnerability of buildings, infrastructure, and architectural assets.

This assessment should take into account a rough estimate of the materials contained in the buildings and infrastructure, in qualitative and quantitative terms. The estimate can be made by analyzing the local building stock, dividing it into homogeneous portions with reference to the various existing building types and—considering the period of construction—hypothesizing construction systems and related materials. Based on this analysis, it will be possible to make a rough estimate of the stock of materials based on reference building types. This assessment can be supported by consulting geographic information systems. (GIS/SIT) available at the regional scale, useful for mapping the building stock, and facilitated by the use of information on the dimensional, construction, and material characteristics of buildings present in historical or cadastral archives, or on documentary sources and scientific literature relating to seismic events or demolition activities. Quantifying and qualifying the stocks of materials contained in the building stock can provide useful information not only in the event of seismic events, but also for better managing the dynamics of building stock transformation (redevelopment, renovation, demolition) in order to promote and potentially plan the reuse and/or recycling of recovered materials and components in the construction and infrastructure sector, with a view to a circular economy. In Europe, some countries have created these inventories, including, for example, Austria and Germany. The assessment could also include different risk scenarios, depending on the different territorial contexts, assuming seismic events of varying intensity. Equally useful could be an examination of the solutions chosen by Austria and Germany in constructing "inventories" on the vulnerability of real estate assets.

³⁴ The evolution of the seismic classification of the Italian territory is so complex that RELUIS (Consortium of the Network of University Laboratories of Seismic and Structural Engineering) has developed a free software, ECS-it, which allows the visualization of the evolution of the seismic classification of the national territory, allowing queries for individual municipalities.

The list of municipalities subject to the regulations was updated after each significant seismic event by adding new municipalities affected by an earthquake. In particular, the update included the following municipalities: Marche (1932), Irpinia (1930, 1962, 1980), Alpagno (1936), and Belice (1968). As a result of these updates, the seismic classification map of Italy was revised, shifting from the areas subject to the regulations shown in Fig. 4.19 to those indicated in Fig. 4.20.

A significant advancement in legislation occurred in 1974 with Law 64, which forms the basis of the current anti-seismic regulations. The law authorised the Minister of Public Works to issue, through ministerial decrees, technical standards for mandatory construction in seismic zones, covering the design, construction, and testing of new buildings, as well as repairs and elevations. Notably, the law allowed for the updating of seismic standards as knowledge advanced. The same provision required the Ministry to update the seismic classification, which, as before, continued to be revised following earthquakes. The most significant example is the 1976 Friuli earthquake, after which much of the Friuli-Venezia Giulia region was included in Italy's seismic map (Fig. 4.21).

Regarding technical standards, the first provisions were issued by the Ministerial Decree of March 3, 1975, supplemented by a series of subsequent decrees.

In the following years, studies conducted as part of the CNR "Geodynamics" Project- which followed the Friuli-Venezia Giulia (1976) and Irpinia (1980) earthquakes- led to a significant increase in knowledge of the country's seismicity and enabled the formulation of a seismic classification proposal. The project's findings were incorporated into a series of Ministry of Public Works decrees approved between 1980 and 1984, culminating in Ordinance No. 3274 of 20 March 2003, which classified the entire Italian territory as seismic (Fig. 4.22), distinguishing four zones with different expected seismic intensity: from zone 1, with a high probability of strong earthquakes, to zone 4, with a very low probability of strong earthquakes.

Fig. 4.19 Seismic classification map of 1909

Fig. 4.20 Seismic classification map of 1974

Fig. 4.21 Seismic classification map of 1984

Fig. 4.22 Seismic classification map of 2003

Since then, the regulations have been regularly updated, culminating in the 2018 Technical Construction Standards, which set out detailed criteria for the design and construction of buildings. Specifically, they require the use of certified materials, static and dynamic analysis of structures, and distinguish between two intervention methods:

- Seismic retrofitting, mandatory for expansions or changes in intended use.
- Seismic improvement, aimed at increasing safety levels without the need to meet new construction standards.

Over time, the following have been added to building legislation:

- The new process of distributing responsibilities between the State, regions, and local authorities, implemented with the so-called "Bassanini laws" of 1997. As a result of the new distribution of responsibilities: the State, through the Department of Civil Protection, is responsible for defining the general criteria for identifying seismic zones and the technical standards for various types of construction; the regions are responsible for identifying and classifying seismic zones.
- The launch in 1989 of the Eurocodes programme by the European Commission and the European Committee for Standardisation ³⁵ which, from 1994 to 1998, published the first

³⁵ Eurocode 8 Timeline: Design of Structures for Seismic Resistance (EC8 - EC8-2G).

- 1989 – Launch of the Eurocodes program by the European Commission and CEN (European Committee for Standardization).
- 1998 – Publication of the first ENV pre-standards for Eurocode 8:
- ENV 1998-1-1 to ENV 1998-1-4 (reinforced concrete, steel, masonry structures, etc.)
- These were not mandatory but were intended for testing and voluntary application.
- 2004 – 2005 – Publication of the final EN versions of the main parts of EC8:
- 2010 – EU member states adopt the Eurocodes as national standards, gradually abandoning previous standards.

pre-standards of Eurocode 8 “Design of structures for seismic resistance” (EC8). The consequence of the publication of the first experimental versions of EC8 is evident in Presidential Decree 380 of 2001³⁶ which replaces Law 64 of 1974. The standard, in fact, adopts a performance-based approach to construction rather than the traditional, purely prescriptive approach, thus demonstrating a strong alignment with European standards. These standards, through the National Annexes, allow each country to define specific technical parameters related to seismicity, climatic loads, building regulations, etc., based on its specific characteristics. All this while maintaining a consistent regulatory framework at the European level. In Slovenia, EC8 was fully implemented in the Slovenian Technical Standards (SIST EN 1998) and became mandatory in 2008.

The second-generation European standards (EC8-2G) are currently being studied and disseminated, and their implementation will be mandatory from 2028. This second generation of Eurocode 8 introduces significant updates in line with the latest developments in seismic engineering.

Among the most notable are:

- the revision of methods for calculating seismic hazard;
- advanced methods for structural analysis;
- the extensive treatment of structural materials (reinforced concrete, steel, timber, masonry, and composite structures);
- detailed criteria for evaluating existing structures.

Let us now see, in essential terms, how this long process has affected the Programme Area.

Friuli-Venezia Giulia

- Before 1976, only a few municipalities, mostly in the Cividale and Tarcento area, were classified as seismic-prone following the 1928 Carnia earthquake.
- The earthquake of 6 May 1976 led to the inclusion of the affected municipalities among the Italian seismic zones. Law No. 546/77, "Regulations for the Reconstruction and Development

-
- 2022 – 2023 – Publication of the second generation of Eurocodes (including the updated EC8), with improvements in advanced seismic analysis, soil-structure interaction, tall buildings, bridges, and critical infrastructure.
 - The second generation Eurocode 8 (EC8-2G) is not yet officially in force in Italy, but is close to completion and should be applicable by 2028, with the definition of the national annexes expected that year. The new sections of the code are being published and are already available on the UNI website, but full implementation of the new regulations will likely take time.

³⁶ Presidential Decree No. 380 of 6 June 2001, "Consolidated text of legislative and regulatory provisions on building matters, which contains "Provisions for construction with particular requirements for seismic zones" and which contains in Chapter IV "Specific provisions relating to the standards for construction in seismic zones, the related supervision, as well as the methods for repressing violations"

of Friuli," expanded the seismic classification, linking it to the municipalities that benefited from reconstruction efforts.

- In the 1980s and 1990s, there were periodic updates to the municipal lists and technical standards (Ministerial Decrees of 24 January 1986 and 16 January 1996).
- O.P.C.M. 3274 of 20 March 2003 (Ordinance of the President of the Council of Ministers) introduced a scientifically based seismic classification (INGV). The entire territory of Friuli-Venezia Giulia is classified as a seismic zone.
- With Resolution No. 2503 of 15 July 2003, the Region implemented OPCM 3274/2003 and approved the new, updated municipal classification.

Veneto

- Before 1976, no municipality in the Veneto region was classified as seismic-prone; not even the municipalities in the Belluno area affected by the Alpago, Cadore, and Comelico earthquakes had been formally included in the national lists.
- In 1986, with the Ministerial Decree of 24 January, which updated the national seismic classification, several municipalities in the province of Belluno were included among the seismic zones.
- In 2003, with O.P.C.M. 3274, which introduced a scientifically based seismic classification, the entire Friuli-Veneto region was declared seismic-prone.
- With Veneto Regional Council Resolution no. 67 of 2003, the Region implemented O.P.C.M. 3274/2003 and approved the new classification. As can be deduced from this, the province of Venice is considered to be at low seismic risk.

Slovenia

- First, it should be noted that Slovenia, as part of the Yugoslav Federation, applied federal technical standards.
- The first comprehensive Yugoslav earthquake code (Federal Regulation on Construction in Seismic Zones) was introduced in 1964, shortly after the major Skopje earthquake of 1963.
- In the following years, periodic updates were made, particularly in 1981, when technical regulation JUS U.J5.046 and other Yugoslav standards for reinforced concrete and masonry buildings were issued.
- In 1991, Slovenia gained independence and initially retained the Yugoslav standards, later introducing adjustments, especially for reinforced concrete and masonry.
- Subsequently, Slovenia gradually adopted EC8, which became mandatory on 1 January 2008 and became the national reference standard.

4.3.2. Construction periods and state of conservation of buildings

The connection between seismic regulations and the period during which an area was subject to the prescribed construction techniques provides a basis for a preliminary assessment of the vulnerability of buildings in the area under review.

In this report, the situation in Friuli-Venezia Giulia and Slovenia are analyzed. The province of Venice— as mentioned, the only NUTS 3 Veneto unit included in the Programme Area – will be omitted, due to the lack of specific information from ISTAT, which provides only aggregate data at the regional level that cannot be directly projected to the province of Venice.

Further clarification regarding the information on Friuli-Venezia Giulia is necessary due to the temporal discrepancy between the years in which compliance with anti-seismic regulations became mandatory—1976 in the earthquake-affected municipalities, 1977 in the municipalities that received reconstruction funding, and 2003 across the entire region— and the years (1970, 1980) for which ISTAT reports the number of homes built in the region. A comparison, if possible for 1976/77, would indicate how many homes in the region can be considered earthquake-proof according to the parameters of the 1974 regulation. Unfortunately, the ISTAT data for 1980 require us to estimate the number of homes built between 1976/77 and those existing in 1980. This discrepancy cannot be quantified precisely, even when considering building permits (PDC/RE)³⁷, because until 1979, ISTAT only considered those granted in the regional capitals and main centres.

³⁷ Beginning in 1935, Istat began a continuous survey of residential construction data, recording the number and main characteristics of dwellings. The survey has undergone several changes over time. Until 1979, it was a partial survey covering only the capital cities and major towns, with surveyors collecting relevant information directly from construction sites, using documentation relating to occupancy permits, usability certificates, and building permits. Data on the quarterly surveys of residential building permits (PDC/RE) have only been available since 2003.

Friuli-Venezia Giulia

We obtain the distribution of housing by year in Italy and Friuli-Venezia Giulia (Table 4.17) using information collected by ISTAT in the Permanent Census of Population and Housing³⁸ and from CRESME estimates.

Table 4.17 Residential buildings by region and construction period as of 2022

Piemonte	966 807	279 504	145 012	113 820	128 644	113 486	61 047	47 309	55 869	22 116
Valle d'Aosta	45 074	8 437	3 800	5 027	6 165	7 163	5 178	3 824	3 627	1 853
Lombardia	1 535 968	216 363	141 427	209 423	270 255	248 137	155 038	117 417	130 580	47 328
Liguria	269 044	83 378	38 749	36 805	40 656	28 777	14 539	9 958	10 606	5 576
Trentino A. A.	223 801	53 814	16 739	20 853	28 712	27 825	20 708	20 123	22 161	12 866
Veneto	1 107 390	123 442	83 006	139 309	209 422	203 522	120 122	86 440	92 013	50 114
Friuli V. Giulia	317 307	48 207	28 760	40 727	49 967	59 294	35 888	20 180	23 340	10 944
Em. Romagna	838 448	113 630	89 945	133 635	150 585	136 482	76 942	54 786	61 804	20 639
Toscana	746 464	188 584	97 675	110 039	110 434	94 118	54 115	35 680	42 854	12 965
Umbria	205 177	41 272	18 810	24 986	29 692	32 407	20 057	15 048	17 667	5 238
Marche	319 693	60 567	35 222	41 720	51 689	53 624	29 426	18 692	20 684	8 069
Lazio	821 498	88 390	62 727	109 879	138 112	166 296	115 218	64 124	56 462	20 290
Abruzzo	359 911	57 566	46 587	52 314	55 725	56 322	36 075	20 989	22 916	11 417
Molise	109 692	28 466	21 348	14 220	11 719	12 059	8 979	5 939	4 585	2 377
Campania	917 495	104 523	81 478	107 179	151 001	166 078	166 537	70 626	44 886	25 187
Puglia	973 475	103 583	93 953	126 772	161 948	200 366	143 904	67 456	49 316	26 177
Basilicata	163 829	26 657	19 194	25 416	22 596	21 156	24 116	11 712	9 188	3 794
Calabria	623 990	74 417	86 635	94 372	95 029	106 789	81 020	40 284	31 301	14 143
Sicilia	1 465 159	98 560	171 546	223 418	259 958	288 221	210 834	103 729	75 153	33 740
Sardegna	528 951	33 147	44 394	70 922	78 524	95 528	83 023	56 701	50 071	16 641
Nord-Ovest	2 816 893	587 682	328 988	365 075	445 720	397 563	235 802	178 508	200 682	76 873
Nord-Est	2 486 946	339 093	218 450	334 524	438 686	427 123	253 660	181 529	199 318	94 563
Centro	2 092 832	378 813	214 434	286 624	329 927	346 445	218 816	133 544	137 667	46 562
Sud	3 148 392	395 212	349 195	420 273	498 018	562 770	460 631	217 006	162 192	83 095
Isole	1 994 110	131 707	215 940	294 340	338 482	383 749	293 857	160 430	125 224	50 381
ITALIA	12 539 173	1 832 507	1 327 007	1 700 836	2 050 833	2 117 650	1 462 766	871 017	825 083	351 474

The table clearly highlights the age of the Italian and Friuli-Venezia Giulia real estate stock. Seventy-two percent of the national residential building stock was built before 1980, and is therefore more than 45 years old. The situation is similar in Friuli-Venezia Giulia, where at the end of 1980 there were 226,955 buildings, equal to 71.53% of those existing at the end of 2022.

Based on the data available in institutional databases, as previously mentioned, it was not possible to determine the number of buildings constructed in Friuli-Venezia Giulia between 1977 and 1980. Furthermore, even if this number were known, it would be even more complex

³⁸ With the 2018 Permanent Census of Population and Housing, Istat surveys, annually rather than every ten years, the main characteristics of the population habitually residing in the area and their social and economic conditions. The Permanent Census of Population and Housing is conducted on a sample basis in 2025 (approximately 1 million families residing in 2,533 municipalities were involved).

to establish how many buildings constructed during that period were based on planning completed and approved before or after the introduction of the seismic zone (1976/77).

However, based on the ISTAT historical series "*Designed and Built Housing, Production Value, and Added Value - Years 1935-2014*", there was a considerable decline in construction in the final part of the decade (Table 4.18). This suggests that the 71.53% of built stock built before 1977 is a slight overestimation.

Table 4.18 Housing designed and built, production value and added value - Years 1935-2014 (Source: ISTAT)

Construction in Italy	
1971	360.596
1972	259.004
1973	196.640
1974	180.698
1975	219.647
1976	184.276
1977	149.413
1978	154.100
1979	136.731

These data on the number of buildings are useful when combined with information on "Residential buildings by state of preservation, type of material used for the load-bearing structure, and construction period" from the 14th General Census of Population and Housing – Resident Population and Housing in Italian Provinces – for the provinces of Gorizia, Pordenone, and Udine. Trieste has been omitted to avoid cluttering the text and because it is the only province without any municipalities in seismic hazard zones 1 or 2. The data refer to 2001, but as the focus is on the period prior to 1976/77, this does not diminish their significance.

Table 4.19 shows that, as of 2001, of the 116,560 buildings constructed in the province of Udine, 21,767 (18.67%) were in a poor or very poor state of repair. Furthermore, only 23,893 were constructed with reinforced concrete load-bearing structures, a construction method that—for the same intensity/PGA—is on average less vulnerable than masonry structures, with the average expected damage increasing more rapidly for masonry classes as seismic action increases. It should be noted that of these 23,893 reinforced concrete buildings, 1,825 were in a poor or very poor state of repair.

From Table 4.20, it can be seen that in 2001, out of 64,412 buildings constructed in the province of Pordenone, 11,710 (18.18%) were in mediocre or poor condition. Moreover, only 10,580 had been built with reinforced concrete load-bearing structures, of which 799 were in mediocre or poor condition.

Table 4.21 shows that in the reference year of 2001 of the 22,278 buildings constructed in the province of Gorizia, 4,179 (18.76%) were in a mediocre or poor state of repair. Furthermore, only 2,447 had been constructed with reinforced concrete load-bearing structures, and of these, 290 were in a mediocre or poor state of repair.

Table 4.19 Province of Udine: residential buildings by state of conservation, material used for the load-bearing structure and construction period (Source: ISTAT: 14th General Census of Population and Housing - Resident Population and Housing in Italian Provinces)

	Ottimo	Buono	Mediocre	Pessimo	
TOTALE					
Prima del 1919	5.401	13.473	7.464	1.096	27.434
Dal 1919 al 1945	2.489	6.931	3.653	500	13.573
Dal 1946 al 1961	4.200	10.356	3.844	286	18.686
Dal 1962 al 1971	6.773	13.021	2.488	127	22.409
Dal 1972 al 1981	13.872	18.277	2.232	77	34.458
Dal 1982 al 1991	10.398	7.209	571	21	18.199
Dopo il 1991	8.216	1.742	118	8	10.084
Totale	51.349	71.009	20.370	2.115	144.843
MURATURA PORTANTE					
Prima del 1919	4.496	11.132	6.640	1.007	23.275
Dal 1919 al 1945	1.751	5.090	2.940	417	10.198
Dal 1946 al 1961	2.360	5.950	2.541	200	11.051
Dal 1962 al 1971	2.599	5.575	1.248	89	9.511
Dal 1972 al 1981	2.962	4.503	694	16	8.175
Dal 1982 al 1991	1.503	1.269	156	10	2.938
Dopo il 1991	1.365	421	38	2	1.826
Totale	17.036	33.940	14.257	1.741	66.974
CALCESTRUZZO ARMATO					
Prima del 1919	-	-	-	-	-
Dal 1919 al 1945	238	526	167	18	949
Dal 1946 al 1961	859	1.812	491	25	3.187
Dal 1962 al 1971	2.230	3.389	522	12	6.153
Dal 1972 al 1981	6.154	6.860	580	10	13.604
Dal 1982 al 1991	5.493	3.295	180	6	8.974
Dopo il 1991	3.845	593	28	3	4.469
Totale	18.819	16.475	1.968	74	37.336
ALTRO					
Prima del 1919	905	2.341	624	89	4.159
Dal 1919 al 1945	500	1.315	546	65	2.426
Dal 1946 al 1961	981	2.594	812	61	4.448
Dal 1962 al 1971	1.944	4.057	718	26	6.745
Dal 1972 al 1981	4.756	6.914	958	51	12.679
Dal 1982 al 1991	3.402	2.645	235	5	6.287
Dopo il 1991	3.006	728	52	3	3.789
Totale	15.494	20.594	4.145	300	40.533

Table 4.20 Province of Pordenone: residential buildings by state of conservation, material used for the load-bearing structure and construction period (Source: ISTAT: 14th General Census of Population and Housing - Resident Population and Housing in Italian Provinces)

	LEGNO	DURO	MURAGLIE	PISSIRIU	
TOTALE					
Prima del 1919	3.330	6.764	3.957	611	14.662
Dal 1919 al 1945	1.518	3.844	2.069	218	7.649
Dal 1946 al 1961	2.445	6.228	2.095	131	10.899
Dal 1962 al 1971	4.628	9.646	1.653	55	15.982
Dal 1972 al 1981	6.234	8.065	896	26	15.220
Dal 1982 al 1991	4.925	2.725	164	1	7.815
Dopo il 1991	5.528	889	39	4	6.460
Totale	28.608	38.161	10.872	1.046	78.687
MURATURA PORTANTE					
Prima del 1919	2.901	5.611	3.421	563	12.496
Dal 1919 al 1945	1.115	3.112	1.776	197	6.200
Dal 1946 al 1961	1.573	4.460	1.617	105	7.755
Dal 1962 al 1971	2.130	5.472	1.068	30	8.700
Dal 1972 al 1981	1.755	3.347	363	10	5.475
Dal 1982 al 1991	853	776	44	1	1.674
Dopo il 1991	971	273	11	3	1.258
Totale	11.298	23.051	8.300	909	43.558
CALCESTRUZZO ARMATO					
Prima del 1919	-	-	-	-	-
Dal 1919 al 1945	78	136	47	2	263
Dal 1946 al 1961	289	666	187	12	1.154
Dal 1962 al 1971	1.324	2.133	262	14	3.733
Dal 1972 al 1981	2.472	2.683	268	7	5.430
Dal 1982 al 1991	2.617	1.247	60	-	3.924
Dopo il 1991	3.059	375	9	-	3.443
Totale	9.839	7.240	833	35	17.947
ALTRO					
Prima del 1919	429	1.153	536	48	2.166
Dal 1919 al 1945	325	596	246	19	1.186
Dal 1946 al 1961	583	1.102	291	14	1.990
Dal 1962 al 1971	1.174	2.041	323	11	3.549
Dal 1972 al 1981	2.007	2.035	264	9	4.315
Dal 1982 al 1991	1.455	702	60	-	2.217
Dopo il 1991	1.498	241	19	1	1.759
Totale	7.471	7.870	1.739	102	17.182

Table 4.21 Province of Gorizia: residential buildings by state of conservation, material used for the load-bearing structure and construction period (Source: ISTAT: 14th General Census of Population and Housing - Resident Population and Housing in Italian Provinces)

	UETIMO	DUALIU	MURATURE	PISSIRIU	
TOTALE					
Prima del 1919	1.407	2.285	1.110	190	4.992
Dal 1919 al 1945	1.143	2.017	973	117	4.250
Dal 1946 al 1961	1.341	2.651	876	71	4.939
Dal 1962 al 1971	1.394	2.525	579	20	4.518
Dal 1972 al 1981	1.557	1.779	234	9	3.579
Dal 1982 al 1991	1.451	742	32	-	2.225
Dopo il 1991	2.097	282	10	-	2.389
Totale	10.390	12.281	3.814	407	26.892
MURATURA PORTANTE					
Prima del 1919	1.172	1.825	961	161	4.119
Dal 1919 al 1945	931	1.621	840	101	3.493
Dal 1946 al 1961	801	1.650	609	53	3.113
Dal 1962 al 1971	580	1.176	321	14	2.091
Dal 1972 al 1981	458	650	74	2	1.184
Dal 1982 al 1991	415	268	17	-	700
Dopo il 1991	546	104	7	-	657
Totale	4.903	7.294	2.829	331	15.357
CALCESTRUZZO ARMATO					
Prima del 1919	-	-	-	-	-
Dal 1919 al 1945	34	50	24	1	109
Dal 1946 al 1961	175	282	76	7	540
Dal 1962 al 1971	318	470	92	1	881
Dal 1972 al 1981	375	453	87	2	917
Dal 1982 al 1991	410	172	4	-	586
Dopo il 1991	542	57	2	-	601
Totale	1.854	1.484	285	11	3.634
ALTRO					
Prima del 1919	235	460	149	29	873
Dal 1919 al 1945	178	346	109	15	648
Dal 1946 al 1961	365	719	191	11	1.286
Dal 1962 al 1971	496	879	166	5	1.546
Dal 1972 al 1981	724	676	73	5	1.478
Dal 1982 al 1991	626	302	11	-	939
Dopo il 1991	1.009	121	1	-	1.131
Totale	3.633	3.503	700	65	7.901

Buildings in Slovenia

The information on Slovenian buildings, reported in Table 29 below, comes from SISTAT³⁹. It shows that 342,709 buildings (Table 4.22) were constructed by 1981—the year the aforementioned JUS U. J5.046 earthquake-resistant regulations came into force. This figure represents 74% of the buildings constructed by 2002.

As can be seen, this figure is very similar to that of Friuli (71.53%, Table 4.17), indicating that the issues are similar and that the joint development of earthquake-resistant technologies is strategically important for the Programme Area.

The significance of seismic risk in Slovenia is further highlighted by the promotion of the POTROG project, which developed tools for assessing the seismic vulnerability of buildings. As part of the project, an application was created that enables rapid, albeit approximate, estimation of the number of damaged buildings and casualties in a seismic event. The application can simulate strong earthquakes anywhere in Slovenia. One case study focuses on the city of Koper; assuming a nighttime earthquake of intensity IX (approximately 6 on the Richter scale, comparable to the earthquake that struck Amatrice), the application estimates that about 2,600 buildings would likely collapse, housing around 10,000 people. A further 11,000 buildings would be severely damaged, housing an additional 31,000 people.

Table 4.22 Buildings with dwellings for permanent residence or occasional use. Total includes unfinished buildings with unknown year of construction., Census of Population, Households and Housing, 2002

	Year of construction	<1900	1901-1918	1919-1930	1931-1945	1946-1960	1961-1970	1971-1975	1976-1980	1981-1985	1986-1990	1991-1995	1996-2000	>2000
SLOVENIJA	463029	72069	14171	20160	22376	51739	66684	45327	50183	38454	35037	21776	19975	4942
Pomurska	37253	3275	1377	1890	1946	4959	5821	4112	4246	3485	2724	1714	1402	297
Podravska	76802	11245	2195	2889	3915	7995	11242	7478	8589	6812	6085	3774	3671	886
Koroška	14913	2120	324	344	531	1869	2340	1346	1540	1252	1371	884	789	z
Savinjska	61068	10138	1374	1821	2407	7115	9069	6176	7391	4867	4507	2972	2559	642
Zasavska	7519	1149	203	371	504	1366	1038	592	612	557	492	304	269	z
Spodnjeposavska	21984	2752	691	726	1054	3034	3088	2254	2456	1934	2001	995	799	z
Jugovzhodna Slovenija	40892	6015	1193	1539	1790	4841	5266	4085	4761	3685	3447	2169	1729	360
Osrednjeslovenska	90864	10719	2142	3532	5260	9783	15609	10143	9386	7388	6753	4248	4655	1217
Gorenjska	41922	6094	1134	1428	2703	5214	6666	4020	4047	3527	3133	1886	1619	442
Notranjsko-kraška	13393	3355	814	656	641	1393	1197	1042	1206	1050	951	566	415	107
Goriška	31776	7604	1590	3963	891	2558	2717	1986	3924	2074	1842	1192	1131	297
Obalno-kraška	24643	7603	1134	1001	734	1612	2631	2093	2025	1823	1731	1072	937	238

³⁹ Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia

5. The economic dimension of seismic risk and measures to reduce it.

5.1. Costs to reduce seismic risk and impact on the national economy

After describing the overall picture of seismic risk in the Programme Area, using national data in the absence of information at NUTS 3 level⁴⁰, it is logical to continue by examining the costs required to reduce this to an acceptable a level.

To this end, the study "Note on seismic risk in Italy: estimate of the number of affected dwellings (and reference population) and costs for their safety," published in 2016 by the National Council of Engineers, is useful.

The study first estimated the number of dwellings in the various seismic zones of the Italian regions (Table 5.1), and then estimated the costs of making them safe (Table 5.2).

Table 5.1 Estimated number of homes at potential seismic risk, by region and by seismic zone (Source: CNI Research Center elaboration on ISTAT CNI data)

Abruzzo	61.516	111.287	120.383		293.186
Basilicata	47.360	69.666	13.145		130.171
Calabria	271.209	201.992	-		473.201
Campania	78.092	782.641	99.315		960.047
Emilia-Romagna	-	241.899	592.648	45.854	880.401
Friuli- Venezia Giulia	22.234	115.868	35.936	99.322	273.360
Lazio	34.211	278.653	692.510	26.389	1.031.764
Liguria	-	52.806	143.603	288.335	484.744
Lombardia	-	33.096	284.511	1.547.622	1.865.228
Marche	2.635	282.703	17.472	192	303.001
Molise	20.319	54.069	10.822	-	85.210
Piemonte	-	41.853	101.773	923.072	1.066.699
Puglia	10.262	151.710	276.422	341.441	779.835
Sardegna	-	-	-	329.500	329.500
Sicilia	70.774	904.634	13.971	77.853	1.067.232
Toscana	-	143.148	605.814	64.216	813.177
Trentino-Alto Adige	-	-	46.666	185.935	232.601
Umbria	25.679	115.245	26.918	2.899	170.741
Valle d'Aosta	-	-	5.800	40.550	46.350
Veneto	-	109.030	478.248	306.431	893.710

Table 5.2 Estimated costs for seismic safety in homes, by region and seismic zone (Source: CNI Research Center elaboration on ISTAT, CNI CRESME, Protezione Civile data)

⁴⁰ NUTS (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) 3 is a territorial level codified by the EU which corresponds to provinces or districts. In some cases – such as Slovenia – these subdivisions do not correspond to territorial public bodies but refer to statistical entities.

Abruzzo	519.608.951	956.819.990	1.026.708.276		2.503.137.217
Basilicata	389.756.074	578.689.566	110.593.193		1.079.038.832
Calabria	2.261.606.036	1.674.589.040			3.936.195.076
Campania	757.085.265	6.495.980.770	842.691.565		8.095.757.599
Emilia-Romagna		1.886.802.360	4.444.537.374	360.037.192	6.691.376.926
Friuli- Venezia Giulia	175.023.026	912.238.866	282.330.683	668.360.083	2.037.952.658
Lazio	298.653.340	2.251.614.507	4.944.840.424	188.586.014	7.683.694.285
Liguria		358.830.381	978.983.635	1.978.397.589	3.316.211.605
Lombardia		244.134.343	2.127.065.643	10.530.581.244	12.901.781.230
Marche	21.979.822	2.286.865.047	145.423.612	1.608.381	2.455.876.861
Molise	180.286.210	473.637.420	94.327.642		748.251.272
Piemonte		259.827.928	726.379.390	6.400.791.351	7.386.998.669
Puglia	82.257.196	1.206.391.434	2.125.295.858	2.952.326.318	6.366.270.807
Sardegna				2.376.413.502	2.376.413.502
Sicilia	562.630.213	7.477.470.927	113.386.798	637.807.857	8.791.295.795
Toscana		1.264.897.651	5.031.170.932	475.004.478	6.771.073.061
Trentino-Alto Adige			272.053.211	1.128.520.230	1.400.573.441
Umbria	238.681.660	1.054.306.951	230.937.694	27.123.598	1.551.049.903
Valle d'Aosta			37.820.498	264.450.404	302.270.902
Veneto		929.716.300	3.857.865.949	2.497.349.977	7.284.937.271

Table 5.2 shows that the estimated cost of securing Italian homes against seismic risk in 2016 was €93.68 billion. Of this amount, €7.285 billion and €2.038 billion were for Veneto and Friuli-Venezia Giulia, respectively. These figures, while considerable, are far lower than the cost of rebuilding even small areas of the peninsula.

To express this last statement in monetary terms, the National Council of Engineers estimated the cost to the state of rebuilding the areas severely damaged by earthquakes at a nominal €70.4 billion. When updated to 2016 to reflect the figure becomes €121.6 billion). The affected areas considered in the analysis were Valle del Belice (1968), Friuli (1976), Irpinia (1980), Marche/Umbria (1997), Molise/Puglia (2002), Abruzzo and Emilia Romagna (2012).

In this regard, the CGIA Research Office in Mestre established that state spending and revenue from the increase in fuel excise duties, earmarked to finance the aforementioned reconstruction, are not negligible.

A comparison of the two financial flows (Table 5.3) clearly shows that the cost of "short-sightedness" in economic policy choices ultimately falls on citizens through increased fuel prices, which persist even after reconstruction is complete. If these resources were allocated to risk reduction, the levy would make ethical sense.

Table 5.3 Earthquakes in Italy: costs and excise duty increases (amounts in million €) (Source: CGIA Research Office and the CNI Research Centre for the cost part)

Evento	Costo del terremoto	Gettito incremento accisa per terremoto
Terremoto del Belice del 1968	2.213	8.612
Terremoto del Friuli del 1976	4.781	78.101
Terremoto dell'Irpinia del 1980	23.518	55.110
Terremoto Marche e Umbria del 1997	11.669	0
Terremoto Puglia e Molise del 2002	1.281	0
Terremoto dell'Abruzzo del 2009	13.700	539
Terremoto dell'Emilia Romagna del 2012	13.300	2.699
Totale	70.462	145.061

5.2. Impact of interventions on the national economy (input-output matrices)

A comparison, with more immediate repercussions, must be made between the expenditure for seismic risk reduction interventions and the reconstruction costs, and their impact on the national economy. The quantification of impacts can be calculated through the analysis of the resource and use tables⁴¹ and their transformation into symmetric tables, the economic input-output matrices. The impacts that can be determined concern: production value, value added, and employment.

Impact on the value of production

The overall impact on the value of production is the sum of the direct, indirect, and induced impacts:

- The direct impact, triggered by spending in the sector (in this case, the construction sector, considering the expenditure to reduce seismic risk), including the sector itself and in the sectors that produce semi-finished products, intermediate products, and other necessary ;
- The indirect impact is the effect on all sectors directly involved in the production process (production of semi-finished products, intermediate products, and necessary services).
- The induced impact arises from the remuneration of labour in sectors directly and indirectly involved in production. Workers' income drives final consumption spending, which subsequently necessitates increased production.

A recent estimate of the impacts of the construction sector on production, added value and employment is provided by CRESME⁴² (Fig. 5.1). It shows that spending one billion euros in the construction sector generates production of approximately 3.35 billion.

⁴¹ ISTAT: THE RESOURCE AND USE TABLES AND THEIR TRANSFORMATION INTO SYMMETRICAL TABLES
METHODOLOGICAL NOTE The resource and use tables "are matrices by branch of economic activity and by branch of homogeneous production that describe in detail the internal production processes and the transactions on the products of the national economy. The two tables provide a detailed picture of the supply of goods and services, both domestically produced and imported, and of the use of goods and services for intermediate or final uses. They also show the added value and all its components generated by the branches of economic activity. They are therefore matrices that highlight the relationship between the branches of economic activity and the branches of homogeneous production through an accurate description of the internal production processes and the transactions on the products of the national economy." The resource and use tables relating to the national economy are constructed by ISTAT.

⁴² CRESME: "Fact-finding investigation into the macroeconomic and public finance effects of tax incentives for construction" Document attached to the hearing in the Fifth Committee (BUDGET, TREASURY AND PLANNING) of the Chamber of Deputies.

Fig. 5.1 Value of production activated for each additional billion euros of construction investments (data in millions of euros)
(Source: CRESME processing based on ISTAT 2017 data)

Impact on the added value

CRESME also provides an estimate of the added value (Fig. 5.2) generated by spending one billion euros in the construction sector. In this table, the added value generated by the sectors directly affected by the spending is divided between the construction sector and the supplier sectors. The estimate indicates that €1 billion spent in the construction sector generates an added value of approximately €1.1 billion.

Fig. 5.2 Added value generated by an additional billion euros in construction investments (in millions of euros) (Source: CRESME processing based on ISTAT 2017 data)

Impacts on employment

The final category of impacts based on the economic input-output matrices is employment. Below, the estimate by CRESME, as reported in the publication cited in the footnote, regarding the employment generated by spending €1 billion in the construction sector (Fig. 5.3) are reported.

An analysis of the input-output tables shows that the return on expenditure in terms of employment is 15,132 units: 8,018 are directly employed in the construction sector, 3,641 are employed in the construction supply branches, and 3,473 are employed in the sectors that work for the supply branches.

If the same impact coefficients are applied to the €93.8 billion expenditure (not discounted) for safety measures, estimated in 2016 by the CNI, it would be obtained: a return of €314 billion in

terms of the impact on the value of national production; a return of €103.13 billion in added value; and an increase in employment of 1.419.419 units.

Fig. 5.3 Employment generated by one billion euros of construction investments (annual work units) (Source: CRESME processing based on ISTAT 2017 data)

5.3. Dynamics of the construction sector and government incentives

In the previous sections, there are:

- demonstrated the significance of the "seismic risk" problem;
- noted that the costs of securing the entire national residential stock would be lower than those of rebuilding small portions of land, which is repeatedly required to address;
- noted that spending on risk reduction would generate increases in production value, added value, and employment, so that the benefits far outweigh the costs.

A logical continuation is to ask whether in the medium to long term - in the absence of specific public interventions - the risk reduction problem could be resolved autonomously through the dynamics of the real estate market activated by private individuals through new constructions.⁴³

Fig. 5.4 shows that over ten years, from 2011 to 2021, Italian residential buildings increased by only 210,835 units, a rise of 1.7%. With this growth, new buildings that meet legal earthquake-resistant requirements will not be able to replace those that do not meet any standards within an acceptable timeframe. Indeed, the state of repair is likely to deteriorate, following the trend shown in Table 4.19, Table 4.20 and Table 4.21.

Fig. 5.4 Italian real estate portfolio in 2011 and 2021 (Source: ENEA elaborations on ISTAT data).

As further evidence, Fig. 5.5, which CRESME uses to illustrate the dynamics of construction investments in Italy from 1992 to 2022, clearly shows that it is not new construction but the renovation of existing buildings that is driving the market. This confirms the belief that reducing seismic risk cannot be solved simply by amending regulations and adopting updated European guidelines. The issue must be addressed within the context of renovation, for which, it should be noted, specific anti-seismic standards are prescribed in the current guidelines.

⁴³ To define a reasonable time for the market to autonomously produce its effects, it must be considered that from 1968 to 2025, Italy has experienced nine major seismic events. Considering those greater than or equal to 6.0 on the Richter scale or those that have caused a significant number of casualties, an earthquake occurs on average every six years and four months.

Fig. 5.5 Construction investment dynamics in Italy (Millions of euros at constant prices (Source CRESME/SI)

In light of the evolution of the Italian real estate stock—represented by ENEA based on ISTAT data in Fig. 5.4 and by CRESME in Fig. 5.5—the answer to the question of whether the problem can be resolved independently through the dynamics of the new construction real estate market, is negative.

Therefore, as a large portion of residential construction investment in Italy relates to renovation or redevelopment, it is necessary to shift the focus from new construction to renovation. Table 5.4 shows that a significant share of the expenditure for this purpose, amounting to 72% of the total, is driven by government incentives. It is therefore necessary to verify whether these contributions have a significant impact on reducing seismic risk.

Table 5.4 Investments in residential building redevelopment: the components of growth (source: CRESME)

	2020	2021	2022	2023*	TOT 2020-23
(a) investimenti complessivi (Mld €)	51,5	82,1	118,5	114,7	366,8
(b) variazioni prezzi	0,4%	18,4%	9,6%	2,5%	
(c) investimenti incentivati realizzati (Mld €)	31	53,7	89,7	89,5	263,9
(c/a) incidenza spesa incentivata	60%	65%	76%	78%	72%

If it is considered how private individuals have used the incentives (Table 5.5), it emerges that only a minimal portion has been allocated for this purpose. In fact, investments made for this purpose—including the Super Sismabonus, which will expire for much of the country on 31 December 2025—amounted to only 5.76% of the total incentivised sum, and this figure also includes a range of interventions associated with earthquake-resistance measures but not directly related to the main purpose. Comparing the Sismabonus to the Home Bonus, the former represents only 0.69% of the latter.

Table 5.5 Estimate of investments activated by tax incentives (2007–2022) (in billions of €) (source: CRESME)

TIPOLOGIA BONUS	1998-2006	2007-2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Totale
BONUS CASA	45,95	86,26	25,39	22,06	24,93	24,38	25,16	25,28	25,15	16,71	26,58	347,85
SISMABONUS	-	-	-	-	-	0,10*	0,08*	0,12*	0,49	1,35	0,55	2,39
ECOBONUS	-	21,92	3,07	3,09	3,31	3,72	3,33	3,48	3,41	7,54	6,82	5,69
BONUS FACCIATE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,62	25,14	0,70	27,46
SUPER SISMA BONUS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,27	3,40	13,67	17,34
SUPER ECOBONUS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,10	12,96	46,29	59,
TOT	45,95	108,19	28,46	25,15	28,24	28,20	28,57	28,88	31,04	67,10	94,61	514,39

These data reveal that, even with incentives, private individuals pay relatively little attention to seismic risk, and the incentive has limited effectiveness in directing spending. This impression is supported by the increased use of the SUPER SISMA BONUS compared to the SISMABONUS, suggesting that the incentive becomes attractive only when it offers very high percentage deductions and covers a broad range of goods and services, not always directly related to earthquake protection. Perhaps, to ensure proper management of public resources and more effective targeting of spending, it would be logical to increase the requirements for housing incentives. For example, one might question whether it makes sense to incentivise facade renovations for a property that is highly vulnerable to seismic activity and would become uninhabitable in the event of a medium-to low-intensity earthquake.

Given the propensity of private individuals to strengthen structures is modest despite incentives, let us now consider the role currently played by the public sector in this area through the financing of Public Housing (Edizia Residenziale Sociale, or EDR).

- Through the PNRR (National Renewable Energy Plan), the State—in addition to co-financing measures such as the Ecobonus, Sismabonus, and Superbonus, which primarily benefit private entities and, to a lesser extent, public bodies—has made a series of financing channels available to public entities managing residential construction. The main ones are:
 - • Innovative Housing Quality Program (PINQUA)⁴⁴ for approximately €2.8 billion;
 - • National Fund for Complementary Investments to the PNRR (PNC) €2 billion.

Specific allocations are then added for hospitals (€900 million), places of worship, cultural heritage, and schools (€800 million).

⁴⁴ PINQUA “Investment 2.3: Innovative program for quality of living: The objective of the investment is the construction of new public housing structures, to reduce housing difficulties, with particular reference to existing public assets, and the redevelopment of degraded areas, focusing primarily on green innovation and sustainability.”

The PINQUA programme has financed 159 projects, distributing resources across different types of interventions⁴⁵. Of these, only 18 allocate part of their assigned resources to seismic research⁴⁶.

The Supplementary Fund, pursuant to Article 1, paragraph 2, letter c), no. 13, and paragraphs 2-septies to 2-decies (Safe, green, and social: redevelopment of public housing), states that the Programme finances various types of redevelopment projects for public housing, including “interventions aimed at verifying and assessing the seismic and structural safety of public housing buildings and implementing seismic improvement or retrofitting projects”.

Unfortunately, the National Plan does not provide aggregate analytical information on funded projects indicating the amount of resources used for seismic safety. Furthermore, many funds have yet to be allocated; for example, in the case of Friuli-Venezia Giulia, the last published call for proposals expired on 21 November 2025.⁴⁷ Overall, however, it appears that the modest tendency to invest in seismic safety is not limited to the private sector but is also common among public entities involved in residential construction.

In this regard, further and decisive confirmation comes from the request made by the Italian government to the European Council, as recently as 2023, for amendments to the Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan. The amended plan covered ten measures, including energy efficiency incentives under the Superbonus. As stated in the Council's approval decision, the fifth amendment requested by Italy concerned Investment 2.1, "Strengthening the Ecobonus and the Sismabonus for energy efficiency and building safety." In its request, Italy clarified that priority had been given to energy efficiency measures, resulting in a reduction in measures aimed at improving seismic efficiency. Moreover, these measures had not been completed within the expected timeframe. More specifically, Italy requested that the intermediate target M2C3-2 for energy efficiency measures be increased to compensate for the elimination of the part relating to measures aimed at reducing seismic risk.

⁴⁵ The investment is divided into two lines of intervention, to be implemented without consuming new land: (i) redevelopment and expansion of social housing, restructuring and regeneration of urban quality, improving accessibility and safety, mitigating housing shortages and increasing environmental quality, using innovative models and tools for management, inclusion, and urban well-being; (ii) interventions on public housing with a high strategic impact on the national territory.

⁴⁶ Source: PNRR Mission Unit of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Sustainable Mobility in collaboration with DIGES (General Directorate for State Construction, Housing Policies, Urban Redevelopment and Special Interventions). “Innovative Quality of Living Program – Projects and Initial Evidence.”

⁴⁷ Call for proposals for funding for local authorities to support interventions funded by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) or the National Supplementary Plan (PNC). Deadline extended to November 21, 2025.

5.4. Reasons for the modest interest in seismic safety

Private motivations

As noted in the previous pages, despite the high seismic risk affecting large areas of Italy and the Programme Area, private investment in reducing the vulnerability of the building stock remains limited. This is particularly concerning, as recent events have shown, when compared to the costs of seismic incidents that frequently occur both in Italy and in the Programme Area. The reasons for this limited interest are complex and include logistical constraints, risk perception, economic issues, and behavioural factors. These reasons are briefly described below. The main constraint is logistical: with traditional strengthening technologies, the building undergoing work – which involves interventions on both the interior and exterior walls – must be cleared of people and property. This requires occupants to relocate during the works, with easily imaginable consequences. This is the primary constraint, as evidenced by the fact that the other reasons are overcome when relocation is not necessary, such as in energy retrofit projects.

Another factor concerns the population's limited perception of seismic risk. Studies conducted by the INGV⁴⁸ show that, even in areas classified as medium-high risk, the risk is often perceived as remote or unlikely, especially in the absence of recent events.

Another important factor is economic constraints. Interventions to reduce seismic vulnerability involve high initial costs, which present a significant barrier, particularly for families with limited spending power. Even with tax incentives, these families may be deterred by the suspicion that some costs will not be uncovered, such as diagnosis, planning, and financial advances.

Some established personal behaviours also play a significant role in decisions not to invest in the prevention of rare events such as earthquakes. Very often, people prioritise immediate benefits over future and uncertain ones; a kind of unrealistic optimism prevails, specifically the belief that negative events will affect "others" more than themselves.

Finally, it is noteworthy that in Italy, a large portion of the building stock consists of condominiums, where extraordinary works require qualified majorities that are difficult to

⁴⁸ The Risk Perception and Communication survey, conducted by the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology (INGV) in 2015, in collaboration with the Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies of the National Research Council (CNR-IRPPS) and the National Institute of Oceanography and Experimental Geophysics in Trieste (OGS), on a national statistical sample of over 4,000 people and funded by the Department of Civil Protection (DPC), highlighted that the perception of seismic hazard in Italy is significantly underestimated. In a seven-point perception scale used in the questionnaire (<http://www.terremototest.it>) in which the score 1 indicates the lowest perception value while the score 7 indicates the maximum, the results of the survey show that the perception of seismic hazard in Italy country is on average 3.24, with non-significant differences, from a statistical point of view, between the regions of the North (3.20), the Centre (3.39) and the South and Islands (3.70).

achieve. Furthermore, in the case of rented properties, the costs of the intervention fall on the owner, while part of the benefits (perceived safety) are enjoyed by the tenant.

In summary, the low propensity to invest in seismic risk reduction arises from a combination of logistical, perceptual, behavioural, and economic factors that are difficult to overcome.

Public entities motivations

Regarding the limited tendency of public entities to implement seismic risk reduction interventions, it is believed this is essentially due to logistical issues. The background of owners is public housing is such that it is unlikely they are aware of seismic risk.

Financial availability is not an absolute constraint, as shown by the largely untapped potential to access resources from PINQUA and the National Complementary Fund for the anti-seismic improvement of publicly owned buildings.

In condominiums where ownership is shared between public entities, such as ATER and municipalities and private entities⁴⁹, public in most cases enjoys the required majorities to decide on the implementation of seismic strengthening.

The logistical challenge persists, particularly in managing the relocation of residents from buildings requiring seismic retrofitting. This is illustrated by the costs incurred by ATER UDINE for relocating tenants from several of its buildings as part of a PINQUA demolition, reconstruction, and land redevelopment project (Table 5.6). Although not directly related to seismic risk reduction, the project is comparable in terms of the logistical and social issues arising from the relocation of residents.

Table 5.6 Costs incurred by ATER UDINE as part of a PINQUA project.

COSTI DIRETTI PINQUA				
DESCRIZIONE		DA COAN	STIMATO*	TOTALE
TRASLOCHI (22 ALL ATER)		57.436,89		
TRASLOCHI (45 ALL DEL COMUNE)			117.484,55	
NET ALLOGGI ATER		1.280,00		
NET ALLOGGI COMUNE			2.618,18	
RIMBORSO SPOSTAMENTI UTENZE (RICHIESTI SU 47 ALL)		6.977,37		
UTENZE PER UNITA' ADIBITA A UFFICIO DEDICATO PINQUA		664,75		
SPESE DEL PERSONALE ATER CHE HA GESTITO I 67 ALLOGGI		89.647,19		
LOCAZIONI	36.911,49			
ASSEGNAZIONI	34.794,02			
PERSONALE TECNICO	9.300,54			
LEGALE	2.552,70			
ISPETTIVO	6.088,44			
		156.006,20	120.102,73	276.108,93

*DATI NON IN CONTABILITA' ATER PERCHÉ DI COMPETENZA DEL COMUNE. STIMATI QUINDI IN MODO PROPORZIONALE AL COSTO DELL'ATER

In addition to the significant travel costs, which in this case were approximately €276,000, one must consider the social issues that typically create many conflicts. In this particular case, such conflicts were avoided thanks to the time ATER staff dedicated to this aspect of the project.

⁴⁹ Usually buyers of apartments previously rented to them by public entities.

Another significant issue concerns the health consequences⁵⁰, such as depression, resulting from moving. It should be emphasised that health issues particularly affect the elderly, who make up a significant proportion of public housing residents.

⁵⁰ This topic is little addressed in national literature but is highlighted in all its complexity in international publications that deal with similar problems.

5.5. Comparison between traditional and CONSTRAIN technologies

Is it possible to overcome the logistical problem while respecting the cost-effectiveness rules specific to the public sector?

We present a comparison between traditional technology and the technology developed in the INTERREG ITALIA SLOVENIA CONSTRAIN territorial cooperation projects for designing a seismic risk reduction intervention on an ATER UD building.

As shown on previous pages, non-seismic safety improvements are often not implemented because people are reluctant to relocate during construction works. By acting only on the exterior of buildings, the "CONSTRAIN" technology enables the work to be carried out without requiring the occupants to relocate.

Even if this preliminary constraint is overcome, given the modest willingness of private individuals to undertake costly work for a risk that can only be quantified probabilistically, the use of the "CONSTRAIN" technology would likely not result in substantial improvements in the seismic safety of residential buildings in the area. A significant contribution to this outcome could come from interventions in public housing.

Public intervention—in addition to ensuring the safety of its tenants and improving the condition of its assets—is appropriate for several reasons, including:

- the huge difference between the cost of a potential reconstruction, already established several times for the Program Area, and that of earthquake protection;
- the marked prevalence of the economic impacts of the expenditure compared to the initial monetary outlays.⁵¹

It is important to consider that, in public construction projects, the economic and socio-health costs of work carried out using different available methodologies are crucial. For this reason, it was necessary to compare the costs of the traditional technology used with those of the technology developed in CONSTRAIN.

Among conventional solutions, the "galvanised steel mesh reinforced cement coating", also known as "rete-betoncino" in Italy, remains one of the most widely used benchmarks. It consists of galvanised welded steel mesh-reinforced cement-based coatings on both sides of the wall. The coatings are connected through the wall by transverse steel anchors.

Reinforced cement coatings must be applied to both sides of the walls; otherwise, they are not effective. This was clearly demonstrated in recent post-earthquake surveys, which showed asymmetric structural responses and detachment of the reinforced coating in such cases. In contrast, the CONSTRAIN project experimentally proved that CRM systems applied to only one side of the wall are effective when properly designed.

⁵¹ Convenience clearly demonstrated through the use of input output matrices

Economic comparison

Direct costs between two systems are compared in sample sheets, which provide an analytical price breakdown. The sheets, included in Annex A highlight the principal cost items and quantities that should be considered.

It should be noted that the calculations use galvanised steel components in the cement-based coating to ensure comparable system durability (45–50 years). Uncoated steel, which was widely used in the past, would modestly reduce material costs but drastically decrease durability due to corrosion (approximately 20–25 years), resulting in nearly double the annual amortisation costs.

A comparison of the direct costs for the basic techniques shows that the CONSTRAIN technology (i.e. the one-side application of Composite Reinforced Mortar) is approximately 25% cheaper than two-sided reinforced-cement coating. The higher cost of the fibre-based composite mesh is offset by lower material consumption and reduced labour time.

Additional costs arise for construction details involving structural discontinuity, such as anchoring into the foundation, across floors, and at wall corners and intersections. These costs are typically higher for the CRM technique due to the use of fibre-based composite materials and stainless steel threaded bars. The impact of these details on the total cost of the strengthening intervention varies from case to case, but does not significantly affect the price difference.

On the other hand, it is also evident that the two-sided reinforced cement coating entails significantly higher (practically doubled) costs associated with the removal of existing plaster, masonry surface preparation, and application of finishes.

When CRM is applied to multi-leaf masonry walls, additional devices (such as artificial diatones) are required to connect the masonry leaves, ensuring confinement. In these cases, the direct costs of CRM are about 10% higher than those of two-sided reinforced cement coating.

The calculations show that the direct costs of CRM on both sides are almost 45–50% higher than those of reinforced cement coating. However, other factors and requirements, such as mechanical and chemical compatibility with the masonry, should also be considered.

In addition to direct costs, other significant economic implications must be considered when selecting strengthening interventions. For example, reinforced cement coating applied to both sides usually requires access to interior spaces and causes significant disruption to building occupants. This necessitates their temporary relocation, either partial or complete, depending on building use, and incurs costs for alternative accommodation, lost productivity in commercial spaces, and management and coordination overheads.

The one-sided CRM application significantly alleviates these issues. In many cases, the intervention can be performed externally with only minimal work required from the inside, resulting in lower non-construction expenses and indirect costs. In terms of inconvenience, it is

comparable to any façade intervention. It can also be combined with a thermal insulation intervention, which occupants appreciate as they perceive direct and more noticeable savings.

The cost comparison was carried out using the current price list for public works in Friuli-Venezia Giulia and the price analyses in ANNEX A, based on a seismic risk reduction project for a building owned by ATER Udine, located at Via Flambro 8, Udine. The property, built using traditional masonry in 1947, was selected because:

- The building shares characteristics with many other public housing buildings in the area and elsewhere in Italy, making it a representative example for the study;
- There are many buildings in the vicinity with similar geometry and characteristics, allowing the study's findings to be extended to other similar contexts;
- The availability of detailed data and information on the building facilitates the analysis and evaluation of necessary interventions;
- Intervening on this building could have a significant positive impact on the local community, improving the living conditions of many residents.

Building volume:

$34.04 \times 9.03 \times (10.80 + 1.80 / 2) = 3,596.36 \text{ m}^3$ (above-ground volume);

$34.04 \times 9.03 \times 1.75 = 537.75 \text{ m}^3$ (underground volume);

Area affected by reinforcement application:

Reinforcement on one side (CRM system): 894.61 m² (above-ground walls);

Reinforcement on two sides (CRM system): 367.54 m² (basement walls);

Rete-betoncino, two sides (traditional system): 894.61 m² (above-ground walls);

Rete-betoncino, two sides (traditional system): 367.54 m² (basement walls);

Details of the materials and labour required to perform the intervention, assuming the use of CONSTRAIN technology and the traditional rete-betoncino technology, are reported in ANNEXES B and C. The summary is shown in Table 5.7.

In summary, considering only the works on the above-ground structure, where the two techniques are directly compared, the costs incurred using the CONSTRAIN technology are €79,675.99, or 33%, lower than those incurred using traditional technology. The savings on the total work amount are less evident (€47,740.04, or 11%) in this specific example, due to the impact of the intervention on the reinforced concrete walls of the basement level.

However, expanding the cost structure to include logistics expenses and the need to relocate residents for the duration of the work, as required by the choice of rete-betoncino – based on the experience in the PINQUA case of ATER UD – makes the CONSTRAIN solution even more cost-effective, with costs 26% lower.

Table 5.7 Summary of cost comparison for the ATER building of via Flambro 8, Udine.

	Traditional technology	CONSTRAIN technology			
ABOVE-GROUND WORKS	240 287.64 €	160 611.65 €	-79 675.99 €	(-33%)	
Structural works	179 097.63 €	130 450.69 €			
Building works	61 190.01 €	30 160.96 €			
BELOW-GROUND WORKS	148 325.34 €	190 941.24 €			
Excavations and backfilling	51 407.08 €	51 407.08 €			
Structural works	82 031.70 €	124 647.60 €			
Building works	14 886.56 €	14 886.56 €			
COMMON WORKS	59 242.17 €	48 562.21 €			
Safety	59 242.17 €	48 562.21 €			
TOTAL WORK AMOUNT	447 855.14 €	400 115.10 €	-47 740.04 €	(-11%)	
TEMPORARY RELOCATION	92 084.00 €	0.00 €			
OVERALL COST	539 939.14 €	400 115.10 €	-139 824.04 €	(-26%)	

Social and health consequences of using the "CONSTRAIN" technology

In many cases, CONSTRAIN strengthening can be carried out only from outside with minimal internal intervention, resulting in lower non-construction expenses and indirect costs. In terms of inconvenience, it is comparable to any façade intervention. It can also be combined with adding thermal insulation, which occupants appreciate due to direct and more noticeable savings.

Furthermore, when temporary relocation of occupants is required, various social costs and consequences arise. Relocation can significantly disrupt daily life, particularly for families with children, elderly residents, or individuals with limited mobility, and can lead to different forms of conflict. The loss of routine, proximity to services, and established social networks can cause stress and reduce overall well-being. International studies highlight an increase in depressive states and other health conditions. Temporary housing solutions may also result in lower living standards or overcrowding, further increasing discomfort and social vulnerability. In some cases, relocation may affect employment and education due to increased travel distances. The temporary relocation of residents can also weaken neighbourhood cohesion and create a perception of instability in the area. For public housing tenants, these effects may be even more pronounced due to pre-existing socio-economic vulnerabilities. Public housing agencies must address these challenges both by implementing forms of engagement that require significant staffing and by accommodating the relocated population's requests, which are rarely inexpensive, regarding the preparation of the spaces to be temporarily occupied. These repercussions can be quantified by analysing the financial statements of the demolition and

reconstruction projects financed by the PNRR (PINQUA Project), which demonstrate their economic significance.

Currently, there is limited information on the psychological distress experienced by people, particularly the elderly, due to relocation; however, international surveys indicate an increase in depression and other conditions.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, this research demonstrated:

- The CONSTRAIN technology can significantly facilitate the implementation of seismic risk reduction work on buildings, which is currently hindered by the very limited willingness of people to undertake such work. This reluctance – evidenced by the minimal use of substantial public funding allocated for this purpose– is largely due to the significant logistical and economic difficulties arising from the need to relocate during the work.
- The cost of implementing the CONSTRAIN technology is lower than that of the traditionally used rete-betoncino technology.

For cross-border cooperation projects, such as those funded by the Interreg programme, the evidence from this report reinforces the importance of combining technical solutions with actions addressing the social and economic dimensions of prevention, in order to reduce the barriers that hinder the adoption of behaviours more consistent with seismic safety in homes.

Acknowledgments

The PRO-SIS project is funded by the Interreg VI-A Italy-Slovenia Programme 2021-2027, co-funded by the European Union.

All the project partners that actively contributed to the project are gratefully acknowledged.

Appendix 1

Municipalities in Friuli-Venezia Giulia, by seismic zone.

Seismic zone 1

MUNICIPALITY	EARTHQUAKE ZONE	Population 01 01 2024	Surface area KM2	Density per KM2
Amaro	1	844	33	25
Andreis	1	245	27	9
Artegna	1	2.878	11	256
Attimis	1	1.641	33	49
Barcis	1	227	103	2
Bordano	1	698	15	47
Buja	1	6.333	26	248
Casteln. del Friuli	1	827	22	37
Cavasso Nuovo	1	1.496	11	141
Clauzetto	1	373	28	13
Fanna	1	1.467	10	143
Forgaria nel Friuli	1	1.689	29	58
Frisanco	1	593	61	10
Gemona del Friuli	1	10.514	56	188
Lusevera	1	597	53	11
Magnano in Riviera	1	2.245	8	269
Maniago	1	11.490	69	165
Meduno	1	1.496	32	47
Montenars	1	483	21	23
Montereale Valcell	1	4.221	68	62
Nimis	1	2.622	34	77
Osoppo	1	2.783	22	124
Pulfero	1	831	49	17
Resia	1	917	119	8
Savogna	1	354	22	16
Taipana	1	567	65	9
Tarcento	1	8.845	35	250
Trasaghis	1	2.088	78	27
Travesio	1	1.827	28	64
Vajont	1	1.640	2	1034
Venezzone	1	1.933	55	35
Vito d'Asio	1	721	54	13
		75.485	1.280	59

Seismic zone 2

MUNICIPALITY	EARTHQUAKE ZONE	Population 01 01 2024	Surface area KM2	Density per KM2
Ampezzo	2	891	74	12
Arba	2	1.295	15	85

Arta Terme	2	2.022	43	47
Aviano	2	9.008	113	80
Brugnera	2	9.277	29	319
Budoia	2	2.521	37	67
Buttrio	2	3.926	18	221
Campoformido	2	7.864	22	359
Caneva	2	6.226	42	149
Capriva del Friuli	2	1.618	6	256
Cassacco	2	2.793	12	239
Cavazzo Carnico	2	954	39	24
Cercivento	2	640	16	41
Chiusaforte	2	594	100	6
Cimolais	2	349	101	3
Cividale del Friuli	2	10.780	51	213
Claut	2	874	166	5
Colloredo di M.A.	2	2.177	22	100
Comeglians	2	424	19	22
Cordenons	2	17.818	56	316
Cormons	2	7.148	35	204
Corno di Rosazzo	2	3.143	13	249
Coseano	2	2.012	24	85
Dignano	2	2.237	28	81
Dogna	2	150	70	2
Dolegna del Collio	2	295	13	23
Drenchia	2	101	12	8
Enemonzo	2	1.261	24	53
Erto e Casso	2	362	52	7
Faedis	2	2.754	47	59
Fagagna	2	5.982	37	161
Farra d'Isonzo	2	1.675	10	163
Flaibano	2	1.086	17	63
Fontanafredda	2	12.900	46	278
Forni di Sopra	2	914	82	11
Forni di Sotto	2	530	94	6
Gorizia	2	33.608	41	814
Grimacco	2	297	16	18
Lauco	2	649	35	19
Majano	2	5.741	28	203
Malborg. Valbruna	2	895	124	7
Manzano	2	6.333	31	204
Martignacco	2	6.861	27	257
Mereto di Tomba	2	2.519	27	92
Moggio Udinese	2	1.615	142	11
Moimacco	2	1.602	12	136
Moraro	2	718	4	201
Moruzzo	2	2.401	18	135
Mossa	2	1.516	6	244

Ovaro	2	1.727	58	30
Pagnacco	2	5.080	15	340
Paluzza	2	1.952	70	28
Pasian di Prato	2	9.241	15	600
Paularo	2	2.338	84	28
Pinzano al Tagl.	2	1.519	22	69
Polcenigo	2	3.109	50	63
Pontebba	2	1.284	100	13
Porcia	2	14.925	30	505
Pordenone	2	52.147	38	1365
Povoletto	2	5.416	38	141
Pradamano	2	3.533	16	222
Prata di Pordenone	2	8.309	23	362
Premariacco	2	3.921	40	98
Preone	2	249	22	11
Prepotto	2	702	33	21
Ragogna	2	2.831	22	129
Ravascletto	2	509	26	19
Raveo	2	437	13	35
Reana del Rojale	2	4.631	20	228
Remanzacco	2	6.013	31	194
Resiutta	2	266	20	13
Rive d'Arcano	2	2.366	23	105
Roveredo in Piano	2	5.801	16	364
Sacile	2	20.030	33	612
S.Daniele del Friuli	2	7.922	35	228
S.Floriano Collio	2	735	11	69
S.Giorgio Richinv.	2	4.538	48	94
S.Giovanni Natis.	2	6.024	24	250
S.Leonardo	2	1.019	27	38
S.Lorenzo Isontino	2	1.485	4	337
S.Martino al Tagl.	2	1.475	18	82
S.Pietro al Natisone	2	2.084	24	87
San Quirino	2	4.272	52	83
San Vito di Fagagna	2	1.664	9	194
Sappada	2	1.313	62	21
Sauris	2	390	41	9
Savogna d'Isonzo	2	1.707	17	101
Sedegliano	2	3.684	50	73
Sequals	2	2.185	28	79
Socchieve	2	861	66	13
Spilimbergo	2	11.778	72	164
Stregna	2	284	20	14
Sutrio	2	1.225	21	59
Tavagnacco	2	14.625	15	953
Tolmezzo	2	9.776	65	151
Torreano	2	2.037	35	58

Tramonti di Sopra	2	267	125	2
Tramonti di Sotto	2	335	86	4
Treppo Grande	2	1.715	11	151
Treppo Ligosullo	2	677	36	19
Tricesimo	2	7.554	18	427
Udine	2	98.304	57	1719
Valvasone Arzene	2	3.960	30	133
Verzegnis	2	847	39	22
Villa Santina	2	2.125	13	164
Vivaro	2	1.329	38	35
Zoppola	2	8.352	46	183
Zuglio	2	535	18	29
		554.775	4.214	132

Seismic zone 3

MUNICIPALITY	EARTHQUAKE ZONE	Population 01 01 2024	Surface area KM2	Density per KM2
Aiello del Friuli	3	2.121	13	159
Aquileia	3	3.152	37	84
Azzano Decimo	3	15.767	51	307
Bagnaria Arsa	3	3.461	19	180
Basiliano	3	5.161	43	120
Bertiolo	3	2.344	26	90
Bicinicco	3	1.792	16	112
Camino al Tagl.	3	1.528	22	68
Campolongo Tap.	3	1.106	11	100
Carlino	3	2.634	30	87
Casarsa Delizia	3	8.258	20	404
Castions di Strada	3	3.672	33	112
Cervignano del Fr.	3	13.680	29	469
Chions	3	5.054	33	151
Chiopris-Viscone	3	703	9	76
Codroipo	3	15.920	75	212
Cordovado	3	2.746	12	228
Doberdò del Lago	3	1.330	27	49
Duino Aurisina	3	8.224	45	181
Fiume Veneto	3	11.821	36	331
Fiumicello Villa Vic.	3	6.293	29	219
Fogliano Redip.	3	2.979	8	376
Forni Avoltri	3	501	81	6
Gonars	3	4.530	20	229
Gradisca d'Isonzo	3	6.428	11	573
Grado	3	7.596	119	64
Latisana	3	13.226	38	350
Lestizza	3	3.605	34	105
Lignano	3	6.901	16	439
Marano Lagunare	3	1.689	87	19

Mariano del Friuli	3	1.447	9	168
Medea	3	947	7	129
Monfalcone	3	30.059	21	1455
Monrupino	3	841	13	67
Morsano al Tagl.	3	2.681	33	82
Mortegliano	3	4.799	30	160
Muggia	3	12.834	14	922
Muzzana del Turgn.	3	2.352	24	97
Palazzolo Stella	3	2.824	35	82
Palmanova	3	5.352	13	403
Pasiano di Porden,	3	7.859	46	172
Pavia di Udine	3	5.468	34	159
Pocenia	3	2.360	24	98
Porpetto	3	2.470	18	137
Pozzuolo del Friuli	3	6.864	34	200
Prato Carnico	3	825	82	10
Pravisdomini	3	3.467	16	214
Precenicco	3	1.426	27	52
Rigolato	3	374	31	12
Rivignano Teor	3	6.250	48	131
Romans d'Isonzo	3	3.568	15	230
Ronchi dei Leg.	3	11.833	17	692
Ronchis	3	1.923	18	105
Ruda	3	2.787	19	143
Sagrado	3	2.124	14	152
San Canzian d'Is.	3	6.023	34	178
San Dorligo Valle	3	5.678	24	234
S.Giorgio di Nogaro	3	7.280	26	281
San Pier d'Isonzo	3	1.940	9	215
S.Vito al Tagl.	3	15.215	61	250
San Vito al Torre	3	1.220	12	102
S. Maria la Longa	3	2.298	20	117
Sesto al Reghena	3	6.311	41	155
Sgonico	3	1.976	31	63
Staranzano	3	7.148	19	380
Talmassons	3	3.825	43	89
Tarvisio	3	3.942	208	19
Terzo d'Aquileia	3	2.708	28	95
Torviscosa	3	2.590	49	53
Trieste	3	198.843	85	2337
Trivignano Udinese	3	1.539	18	83
Turriaco	3	2.780	5	537
Varmo	3	2.647	35	76
Villesse	3	1.607	12	133
Visco	3	830	4	235
		564.356	2.439	231

Appendix 2

Municipalities in Friuli-Venezia Giulia: seismic zone and climate area

MUNICIPALITY	Seismic Z	Climatic Z
Aiello del Friuli	3	E
Aquileia	3	E
Azzano Decimo	3	E
Bagnaria Arsa	3	E
Basiliano	3	E
Bertiolo	3	E
Bicinicco	3	E
Camino al Tagliamento	3	E
Campolongo Tapogliano	3	E
Carlino	3	E
Casarsa della Delizia	3	E
Castions di Strada	3	E
Cervignano del Friuli	3	E
Chions	3	E
Chiopris-Viscone	3	E
Codroipo	3	E
Cordovado	3	E
Doberdò del Lago	3	E
Duino Aurisina	3	E
Fiume Veneto	3	E
Fiunicello Villa Vicentina	3	E
Fogliano Redipuglia	3	E
Forni Avoltri	3	F
Gonars	3	E
Gradisca d'Isonzo	3	E
Grado	3	E
Latisana	3	E
Lestizza	3	E
Lignano Sabbiadoro	3	E
Marano Lagunare	3	E
Mariano del Friuli	3	E
Medea	3	E
Monfalcone	3	E
Monrupino	3	F
Morsano al Tagliamento	3	E
Mortegliano	3	E
Muggia	3	E
Muzzana del Turgnano	3	E
Palazzolo dello Stella	3	E
Palmanova	3	E
Pasiano di Pordenone	3	E

MUNICIPALITY	Seismic Z	Climatic Z
Grimacco	2	E
Lauco	2	F
Majano	2	E
Malborghetto Valbruna	2	F
Manzano	2	E
Martignacco	2	E
Mereto di Tomba	2	E
Moggio Udinese	2	F
Moimacco	2	E
Moraro	2	E
Moruzzo	2	E
Mossa	2	E
Ovaro	2	F
Pagnacco	2	E
Paluzza	2	F
Pasian di Prato	2	E
Paularo	2	F
Pinzano al Tagliamento	2	E
Polcenigo	2	E
Pontebba	2	F
Porcia	2	E
Pordenone	2	E
Povoletto	2	E
Pradamano	2	E
Prata di Pordenone	2	E
Premariacco	2	E
Preone	2	F
Prepotto	2	E
Ragogna	2	E
Ravascletto	2	F
Raveo	2	F
Reana del Rojale	2	E
Remanzacco	2	E
Resiutta	2	F
Rive d'Arcano	2	E
Roveredo in Piano	2	E
Sacile	2	E
San Daniele del Friuli	2	E
San Floriano del Collio/Števerjan	2	E
San Giorgio della Richinvelda	2	E
San Giovanni al Natisone	2	E

Pavia di Udine	3	E
Pocenia	3	E
Porpetto	3	E
Pozzuolo del Friuli	3	E
Prato Carnico	3	F
Pravisdomini	3	E
Precenicco	3	E
Rigolato	3	F
Rivignano Teor	3	E
Romans d'Isonzo	3	E
Ronchi dei Legionari	3	E
Ronchis	3	E
Ruda	3	E
Sagrado	3	E
San Canzian d'Isonzo	3	E
San Dorligo della Valle	3	E
San Giorgio di Nogaro	3	E
San Pier d'Isonzo	3	E
San Vito al Tagliamento	3	E
San Vito al Torre	3	E
Santa Maria la Longa	3	E
Sesto al Reghena	3	E
Sgonico	3	E
Staranzano	3	E
Talmassons	3	E
Tarvisio	3	F
Terzo d'Aquileia	3	E
Torviscosa	3	E
Trieste	3	E
Trivignano Udinese	3	E
Turriaco	3	E
Varmo	3	E
Villesse	3	E
Visco	3	E
Ampezzo	2	F
Arba	2	E
Arta Terme	2	F
Aviano	2	E
Brugnera	2	E
Budoia	2	E
Buttrio	2	E
Campoformido	2	E
Caneva	2	E
Capriva del Friuli	2	E
Cassacco	2	E
Cavazzo Carnico	2	E
Cervento	2	F

San Leonardo	2	E
San Lorenzo Isontino	2	E
San Martino al Tagliamento	2	E
San Pietro al Natisone	2	E
San Quirino	2	E
San Vito di Fagagna	2	E
Sappada	2	F
Sauris	2	F
Savogna d'Isonzo	2	E
Sedegliano	2	E
Sequals	2	E
Socchieve	2	F
Spilimbergo	2	E
Stregna	2	F
Sutrio	2	F
Tavagnacco	2	E
Tolmezzo	2	F
Torreano	2	E
Tramonti di Sopra	2	F
Tramonti di Sotto	2	F
Treppo Grande	2	F
Treppo Ligosullo	2	E
Tricesimo	2	E
Udine	2	E
Valvasone Arzene	2	E
Verzegnis	2	F
Villa Santina	2	F
Vivaro	2	E
Zoppola	2	E
Zuglio	2	F
Amaro	1	E
Andreis	1	F
Artegna	1	E
Attimis	1	E
Barcis	1	F
Bordano	1	E
Buja	1	E
Castelnovo del Friuli	1	E
Cavasso Nuovo	1	E
Clauzetto	1	F
Fanna	1	E
Forgaria nel Friuli	1	E
Frisanico	1	F
Gemona del Friuli	1	E
Lusevera	1	F
Magnano in Riviera	1	E
Maniago	1	E

PRO-SIS

Chiusaforte	2	F
Cimolais	2	F
Cividale del Friuli	2	E
Claut	2	F
Colloredo di Monte Albano	2	E
Comeglians	2	F
Cordenons	2	E
Cormons	2	E
Corno di Rosazzo	2	E
Coseano	2	E
Dignano	2	E
Dogna	2	F
Dolegna del Collio	2	E
Drenchia	2	F
Enemonzo	2	F
Erto e Casso	2	F
Faedis	2	E
Fagagna	2	E
Farra d'Isonzo	2	E
Flaibano	2	E
Fontanafredda	2	E
Forni di Sopra	2	F
Forni di Sotto	2	F
Gorizia	2	E

Meduno	1	E
Montenars	1	F
Montereale Valcellina	1	E
Nimis	1	E
Osoppo	1	E
Pulfero	1	E
Resia	1	F
Savogna	1	E
Taipana	1	F
Tarcento	1	E
Trasaghis	1	E
Travesio	1	E
Vajont	1	E
Venezzone	1	E
Vito d'Asio	1	F

PRO-SIS Report 3.5 - ANNEX A - Examples of price analyses

Italian price analysis

PA.01 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – GALVANIZED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR					
<p>Two-sided structural reinforcement of masonry or concrete walls using a cement plaster with a variable thickness of 30 mm to 70 mm, combined with galvanized welded wire mesh Ø6, 20x20 cm, including transverse passing-through connections 6Ø6/m² in Ø10 holes.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of existing plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the wall surface; drilling of holes at a rate no less than 6/m²; insertion of the transverse connections described above; application of the concrete layer, and all other operations necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with the recognized standards of workmanship</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at wall intersections with horizontal and vertical structural elements Scaffolding, platforms, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the works, as well as any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on both sides of the wall and for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. The price is applied per square meter of wall.</p>			<p>Masonry Concrete steel mesh steel bars</p>		
CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	CEMENT MORTAR FOR WALL CONSOLIDATION, average thickness of 5 cm.	m ²	2.00	26.03 €	52.06 €
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled – Electro-welded mesh Ø6, 20x20 cm	Kg.	4.880	1.96 €	9.56 €
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled - Ribbed steel bars for continuous transverse connections, 6Ø6/m ² , L= 0.8 m	Kg.	1.065	2.00 €	2.13 €
Materials	Surcharge for hot-dip galvanizing of steel elements	Kg.	5.945	2.00 €	11.89 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar, type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	0.855	2.60 €	2.22 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.25 €	1.25 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					148.04 €
	Transport expenses	2%			2.96 €
	General expenses	15%			22.65 €
	Company profit	10%			17.36 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 191.01 €

PA.01.1 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – GALVANIZED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR
Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors

Two-sided structural reinforcement - galvanized steel reinforced cement mortar coating.
 Surcharge for the execution of the connection of the reinforced coating with the foundation and across floors, by using galvanized ribbed steel bars Ø8, B450C, applied at a rate of 4/m at both wall sides. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the coating of the reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both sides of the wall.

The price is applied per meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled - Ribbed steel bars, L= 0.9 m, 4/m	Kg.	2.844	2.00 €	5.69 €
Materials	Surcharge for hot-dip galvanizing of steel elements	Kg.	2.844	2.00 €	5.69 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar, type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	1.62	2.60 €	4.21 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	3.50 €	0.21 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	27.20 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	30.28 €	1.82 €
					19.25 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.38 €
	General expenses	15%			2.94 €
	Company profit	10%			2.26 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m	24.83 €

PA.01bis STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – UNPROTECTED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR

Two-sided structural reinforcement of masonry or concrete walls using a cement plaster with a variable thickness of 30 mm to 70 mm, combined with welded wire mesh $\varnothing 6$, 20x20 cm, including transverse passing-through connections $6\varnothing 6/m^2$ in $\varnothing 10$ holes.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of existing plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the wall surface; drilling of holes at a rate no less than 6/m²; insertion of the transverse connections described above, at a rate of not less than 6/m²; application of the concrete layer, and all other operations necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with the recognized standards of workmanship

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at wall intersections with horizontal and vertical structural elements Scaffolding, platforms, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the works, as well as any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both sides of the wall and for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm.

The price is applied per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	CEMENT MORTAR FOR WALL CONSOLIDATION, average thickness of 5 cm.	m ²	2.00	26.03 €	52.06 €
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled – Electro-welded mesh $\varnothing 6$, 20x20 cm	Kg.	4.880	1.96 €	9.56 €
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled - Ribbed steel bars for continuous transverse connections, $6\varnothing 6/m^2$, L= 0.8 m	Kg.	1.065	2.00 €	2.13 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar, type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	0.855	2.60 €	2.22 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.25 €	1.25 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					136.15 €
	Transport expenses	2%			2.72 €
	General expenses	15%			20.83 €
	Company profit	10%			15.97 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 175.67 €

PA.01.1bis STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – UNPROTECTED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR
Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors

Two-sided structural reinforcement - unprotected steel reinforced cement mortar coating.
 Surcharge for the execution of the connection of the reinforced coating with the foundation and across floors, by using unprotected steel ribbed bars Ø8, B450C, applied at a rate of 4/m at both wall sides. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the coating of the reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both sides of the wall.
 The price is applied per meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled - Ribbed steel bars, L= 0.9 m, 4/m	Kg.	2.844	2.00 €	5.69 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar, type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	1.620	2.60 €	4.21 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	3.50 €	0.21 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	27.20 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	30.28 €	1.82 €
					13.56 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.27 €
	General expenses	15%			2.07 €
	Company profit	10%			1.59 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m	17.49 €

PA.02

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
One-sided for single-leaf masonry

One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a Ø12 mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments <3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm.

Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	40.00	0.45 €	18.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	1.00	46.78 €	46.78 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.58	3.50 €	2.03 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.10 €	1.10 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.58	27.20 €	15.78 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.55	30.28 €	16.65 €
					100.34 €
	Transport expenses	2%			2.01 €
	General expenses	15%			15.35 €
	Company profit	10%			11.77 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 129.47 €

PA.02.1 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER and ARTIFICIAL DIATONES - One-sided for multiple-leaf masonry

One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a $\varnothing 12$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 4/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments <3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

These components are combined with artificial diatons at a rate of 2/m², consisting of a core of flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S, or equivalent, installed in non-through transverse holes with a diameter of 50 mm, into which a stainless steel M16 bar is embedded, fitted with a 50 mm diameter perforated metal washer, 4 mm thick.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish.

Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the GFRP transverse connections, at a rate no less than 4/m², and of artificial ties, in a quantity not less than 2/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	40.00	0.45 €	18.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 4/m ²); GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (n° 4/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	1.00	41.68 €	41.68 €
Materials	STAINLESS STEEL type AISI 316 - M16 bars, length =60 cm (2/m ²)	Kg.	1.596	12.00 €	19.15 €
Materials	STAINLESS STEEL type AISI 316 - M16 bolt with washer, diameter 150 mm, thickness 4 mm (2/m ²)	Kg.	1.200	21.75 €	26.10 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	0.798	0.80 €	0.64 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.68	3.50 €	2.38 €
Rentals	Bare rental of water-cooled rotary percussion core drilling equipment	h	0.50	19.50 €	9.75 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.10 €	1.10 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.68	27.20 €	18.50 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.65	30.28 €	19.68 €
					156.98 €
	Transport expenses	2%			3.14 €
	General expenses	15%			24.02 €
	Company profit	10%			18.41 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m² 202.55 €

PA.03 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided

Two-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for transversal passing-through connection on a $\varnothing 24$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	80.00	0.45 €	36.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices(n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	2.00	46.78 €	93.56 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	2.00	1.10 €	2.20 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					200.68 €
	Transport expenses	2%			4.01 €
	General expenses	15%			30.70 €
	Company profit	10%			23.54 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 258.94 €

PA.03.1 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided with steel ties

Two-sided structural reinforcement of concrete walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, metal connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBMesh66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.
- Stainless steel connectors for transverse connections, at a rate of 6/m², consisting of M8 threaded rods passing through $\varnothing 12$ holes, with 50x1.5 mm washer and nut, grade 8.8, at both wall sides.
- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;
- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with hydraulic cement mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 5 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 25 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	CEMENT MORTAR FOR WALL CONSOLIDATION, average thickness of 5 cm.	m ²	2.00	26.03 €	52.06 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBMesh 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices(n° 6/m ²)	m ²	2.00	23.34 €	46.68 €
Materials	Stainless steel type AISI 316 - M8 bars, average length 50 cm (n° 6/m ²)	Kg.	1.183	17.79 €	21.04 €
Materials	Stainless steel type AISI 316 - M8 bolt with 50 mm diameter, 1.5 mm thick washer (n° 6/m ²)	Kg.	0.555	17.79 €	9.86 €
Materials	Chemical vinylester anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.339	23.00 €	7.80 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	2.00	1.10 €	2.20 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					208.57 €
	Transport expenses	2%			4.17 €
	General expenses	15%			31.91 €
	Company profit	10%			24.46 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m²	269.11 €

PA.04

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
Surcharge for corner connection

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of connections at masonry corners, by using the corner element FBANG66X66T96 by Fibrenet, or equivalent, featuring CE marking, preformed with a 90° bend, consisting of a square mesh with 66x66 mm openings, manufactured with Alkali-Resistant glass roving and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with nominal strand diameter exceeding 3 mm and a width of 33 cm per side. Tensile strength of the composite ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of the individual bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile modulus of elasticity $\geq 25,000$ N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of the individual bar ≥ 4.14 kN, average elongation at failure 1.78%, characteristic node tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity in humid, alkaline, and saline environments $< 8\%$.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: All that is necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with best practice.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment required for the execution of the work, any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and anything else not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Corner element in GFRP FBANG66X66T96AR, 33 cm width per side	m	1.00	17.75 €	17.75 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	27.20 €	2.72 €
					20.47 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.41 €
	General expenses	15%			3.13 €
	Company profit	10%			2.40 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 26.41 €

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

PA.05 Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors, and across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of the connections of the CRM system with the foundation and across floors, as well as across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections, by using M8 stainless steel threaded bars in Ø12 diameter holes, and thermosetting vinylesterepoxy resin, applied at a rate of 3/m. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents., and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 90 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.065	17.79 €	18.94 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.203	23.00 €	4.68 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	3.50 €	0.21 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	27.20 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	30.28 €	1.82 €
					27.28 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.55 €
	General expenses	15%			4.17 €
	Company profit	10%			3.20 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m 35.20 €

PA.06 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
Surcharge for connection across unsymmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of wall T-junctions using M8 stainless steel threaded bars embedded in a passing-through hole of diameter Ø12, M8 bolt, 50x1.5 washer, load-distribution device made of preformed mesh in glass fiber reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, calculated at 3/m. The bar is anchored to the masonry at the hole and embedded in the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 80 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.170	17.79 €	20.81 €
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 bolt + washer diameter 50 mm thickness 1.5 mm (3/ml)	Kg.	0.069	17.79 €	1.23 €
Materials	GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (3/m);	m ²	0.27	17.75 €	4.79 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.170	23.00 €	3.90 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.10	3.50 €	0.35 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	27.20 €	2.72 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.10	30.28 €	3.03 €
					36.83 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.74 €
	General expenses	15%			5.64 €
	Company profit	10%			4.32 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 47.52 €

PA.02 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER					
One-sided for single-leaf masonry					
<p>One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Preformed mesh</u> made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%. - GFRP "L" shape composite material <u>connectors</u> FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a $\varnothing 12$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%. - <u>Load distribution devices</u> made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection; - <u>Chemical anchor</u> for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. <p>The system is completed with premixed lime-based <u>plaster mortar</u> for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.</p>					
CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	40.00	0.45 €	18.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	1.00	46.78 €	46.78 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.58	2.47 €	1.43 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	0.82 €	0.82 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.58	22.51 €	13.06 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.55	24.36 €	13.40 €
Transport	Transport expenses				2.18 €
					95.66 €
	General expenses	15%			14.35 €
	Company profit	10%			9.57 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 119.58 €

PA.03 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided

Two-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBMesh66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for transversal passing-through connection on a $\varnothing 24$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	80.00	0.45 €	36.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBMesh 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices(n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	2.00	46.78 €	93.56 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	2.47 €	2.87 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	2.00	0.82 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	22.51 €	26.11 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	24.36 €	26.80 €
Transport	Transport expenses				1.91 €
					188.87 €
	General expenses	15%			28.33 €
	Company profit	10%			18.89 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m² 236.09 €

PA.04

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
Surcharge for corner connection

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of connections at masonry corners, by using the corner element FBANG66X66T96 by FibreNet, or equivalent, featuring CE marking, preformed with a 90° bend, consisting of a square mesh with 66x66 mm openings, manufactured with Alkali-Resistant glass roving and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with nominal strand diameter exceeding 3 mm and a width of 33 cm per side. Tensile strength of the composite ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of the individual bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile modulus of elasticity $\geq 25,000$ N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of the individual bar ≥ 4.14 kN, average elongation at failure 1.78%, characteristic node tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity in humid, alkaline, and saline environments $< 8\%$.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: All that is necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with best practice.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment required for the execution of the work, any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and anything else not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Corner element in GFRP FBANG66X66T96AR, 33 cm width per side	m	1.00	17.75 €	17.75 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	22.51 €	2.25 €
					20.00 €
	General expenses	15%			3.00 €
	Company profit	10%			2.00 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m 25.00 €

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

PA.05 Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors, and across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of the connections of the CRM system with the foundation and across floors, as well as across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections, by using M8 stainless steel threaded bars in Ø12 diameter holes, and thermosetting vinylesterepoxy resin, applied at a rate of 3/m. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents., and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 90 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.065	13.34 €	14.21 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.203	23.00 €	4.68 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	2.47 €	0.15 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	22.51 €	1.35 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	24.37 €	1.46 €
					21.85 €
	General expenses	15%			3.28 €
	Company profit	10%			2.18 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 27.31 €

PA.06

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

Surcharge for connection across unsymmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of wall T-junctions using M8 stainless steel threaded bars embedded in a passing-through hole of diameter Ø12, M8 bolt, 50x1.5 washer, load-distribution device made of preformed mesh in glass fiber reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, calculated at 3/m. The bar is anchored to the masonry at the hole and embedded in the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 80 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.170	13.34 €	15.61 €
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 bolt + washer diameter 50 mm thickness 1.5 mm (3/ml)	Kg.	0.069	13.34 €	0.93 €
Materials	GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (3/m);	m ²	0.27	17.75 €	4.79 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.170	23.00 €	3.90 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.10	2.47 €	0.25 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	22.51 €	2.25 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.10	24.37 €	2.44 €
					30.16 €
	General expenses	15%			4.52 €
	Company profit	10%			3.02 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 37.70 €

PRO-SIS Report 3.5 - ANNEX B - Bill of quantities for the strengthening of the building of ATER in Udine by using the CONSTRAIN-PROSIS technology

N.	CODE	DESCRIPTION OF WORKS AND SUPPLIES	UNIT	SIMILAR	LENGTH	WIDTH	HEIGHT	QUANTITY	PRICE	AMOUNT
	L1	WORKS ABOVE GROUND								
	02	Structural works								
1	20.6.HH2.09	GALVANIZED STEEL COMPONENTS FOR LIGHT METALWORK, WITH WEIGHT BELOW 20 kg/m Prefabricated steel components for railings, guardrails, and similar items; for stairs and doors of all sizes; walkways with a unit weight below 20 kg/m, manufactured according to the drawings and specifications provided by the Site Supervisor, constructed using tubular steel sections with circular, square, or rectangular profiles; flat, square, and round bars; L-, T-, U-, and Z-shaped sections; electro-welded gratings and steel sheets for cladding and pedestrian walkways. Supplied and installed including: hot-dip galvanizing upon completion of fabrication; cutting waste; hardware for hinges and handles; locks; transport to the place of installation; unloading and installation at any height, including on-site welding; masonry work support; and all other related services, supplies, and charges.								
		<i>Reinforcement saddles for RC beams in terrace areas</i>	Kg	420.00				420.00		
		Total	Kg					420.00	€ 14.67	€ 6 161.40
2	PA.02 (see the attached detailed price analysis)	<p>STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - One-sided for single-leaf masonry One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%. - GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a Ø12 mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments <3%. - Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection; - Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. <p>The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements. Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.</p>								
		<i>EXTERNAL WALLS</i>								
		<i>West Elevation – Front</i>	m2		34.04		9.88	336.32		
		<i>To be deducted</i>	m2					0.00		
		<i>Terraces</i>	m2	4.00	2.45		9.80	-96.04		
		<i>To be added</i>	m2					0.00		
		<i>East Elevation – Rear</i>	m2		34.04		9.88	336.32		
		<i>North Elevation</i>	m2		9.03		9.88	89.22		
		<i>South Elevation</i>	m2		9.03		9.88	89.22		
		<i>INTERNAL WALLS</i>								
		<i>Above-ground floors</i>	m2	3.00	15.88		2.93	139.59		
		Total	m2					894.61	€ 129.47	€ 115 824.95

L2		BELOW-GROUND WORKS								
01		Excavations and backfilling								
	11.7.CP1.01	FOUNDATION EXCAVATION IN SOIL OF ANY NATURE Execution of foundation excavation in a restricted section in soil of any nature and consistency, including boulders with a volume of less than 0.5 m ³ , excluding soft rock and hard rock requiring blasting, whether dry or wet, also in the presence of water of any type, origin, and quantity, for the construction of foundations for structures in general and building foundations, for the laying of pipelines and prefabricated elements, carried out to depths of up to 2 m relative to the stripping level, including the removal of shrubs and stumps, topsoil stripping and recovery, water pumping, any necessary shoring and bracing of the sides, formation of slopes where required, loading and transport within the site of suitable excavated material, including topsoil, for backfilling and embankments, properly shaped and compacted. Any additional operations for the reuse of excavated material or the removal of material deemed unsuitable by the Works Supervisor shall be compensated separately.								
14	11.7.CP1.01.A	Also in the presence of water (water depth up to 20 cm).								
			WEST side	m3	1.79	34.04			60.86	
			EST side	m3	1.79	34.04			60.86	
			NORTH side	m3	1.79	9.03			16.15	
			SOUTH side	m3	1.79	9.03			16.15	
			Total	m3					154.02	€ 20.19 € 3 109.63
	11.7.CP1.06	MANUAL FOUNDATION EXCAVATION IN SOIL OF ANY NATURE INSIDE BUILDINGS Execution of manual excavation for the construction of foundations for structures in general and for the laying of pipelines inside buildings, in soil of any nature and consistency, including boulders up to 0.5 m ³ and soft rock removable with pick or point tools, excluding hard rock requiring blasting, whether dry or wet, also in the presence of water of any type, origin, and quantity, for depths up to 2 m from the excavation level. This includes shoring and bracing of the sides, preservation and protection of any existing installations such as pipelines, ducts, cables, structures, archaeological finds, etc., formation of slopes, and backfilling. Any additional operations for the reuse of excavated material or the removal of material deemed unsuitable by the Works Supervisor shall be compensated separately.								
15	11.7.CP1.06.A	Also in the presence of water (water depth up to 20 cm).								
			EAST lateral rooms	m3	2.00	3.36	3.97	2.10	56.02	
			WEST lateral rooms	m3	2.00	3.91	3.96	2.10	65.03	
				m3	2.00	1.15	1.66	2.10	8.02	
			EAST central rooms	m3	2.00	3.01	3.97	2.10	50.19	
			WEST central rooms	m3	2.00	3.91	3.96	2.10	65.03	
				m3	2.00	1.15	1.66	2.10	8.02	
			Total	m3					252.31	€ 145.25 € 36 648.20
	11.8.CP1.12	DELIVERY OF EXCAVATED MATERIAL FROM THE SITE TO AUTHORIZED TREATMENT AND RECOVERY FACILITIES Transport and delivery of inert waste material resulting from site activities to an authorized waste treatment and recovery facility, including all administrative requirements for handling, transport within a distance of up to 15 km, and delivery to the treatment plant (waste to be delivered to facilities authorized for treatment in accordance with current regulations, Legislative Decree 152/06 as amended and supplemented, and Regional Law 30/87 as amended and supplemented).								
			see item n. 15	m3	252.31				252.31	
			Total	m3					252.31	€ 46.17 € 11 649.25
		Total Excavations and Backfilling								€ 51 407.08

02	Structural works									
17	PA.03.1 (see the attached detailed price analysis)	<p>STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided with steel ties</p> <p>Two-sided structural reinforcement of concrete walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, metal connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBMESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%. - Stainless steel connectors for transverse connections, at a rate of 6/m², consisting of M8 threaded rods passing through Ø12 holes, with 50x1.5 mm washer and nut, grade 8.8, at both wall sides. - Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection; - Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. <p>The system is completed with premixed hydraulic cement mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 5 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 25 MPa.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements. Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.</p>								
		<i>Exterior walls</i>								
		<i>Wall – east side</i>	<i>m2</i>		<i>34.04</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>71.48</i>		
		<i>Wall – west side</i>	<i>m2</i>		<i>34.04</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>71.48</i>		
		<i>Wall – north side</i>	<i>m2</i>		<i>9.03</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>18.96</i>		
		<i>Wall – south side</i>	<i>m2</i>		<i>9.03</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>18.96</i>		
		<i>Interior walls</i>								
		<i>Central wall – long side</i>	<i>m2</i>	<i>2.00</i>	<i>12.52</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>52.58</i>		
		<i>Central walls – short side – opposite staircases</i>	<i>m2</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>3.97</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>33.35</i>		
			<i>m2</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>2.97</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>24.95</i>		
		<i>Walls – stair side</i>	<i>m2</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>3.36</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>28.22</i>		
			<i>m2</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>5.66</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>47.54</i>		
		<i>Total</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>367.54</i>	€ <i>269.11</i>	€ <i>98 909.23</i>

			-	1.00				1.00		
			Total	-				1.00	€ 743.82	€ 743.82
33	99.1.XB1.01.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first								
			/ month	5.00				5.00		
			Total	/ month				5.00	€ 280.51	€ 1 402.55
	99.1.XB1.05	CONSTRUCTION SITE BOX FOR SANITARY FACILITIES DIM. 2.4 × 2.7 × 2.4 m Supply and installation of a construction site box for sanitary facilities, consisting of a base structure elevated from the ground with folded steel profiles, roof and cladding with sandwich panels made of inner and outer sheet metal and central insulation (minimum 40 mm), internal partitions in sandwich panels, aluminum fixtures, wooden floor covered with PVC. Complete with electrical, water (hot and cold), and sewage systems, electric heating and cooling, equipped with one shower, one WC, one washbasin, electric boiler, and accessories. Approximate dimensions 2.4 × 2.7 × 2.4 m. Includes transport, assembly, dismantling, cleaning, maintenance and management costs, and preparation of the support base.								
34	99.1.XB1.05.A	Price – first month								
			Total	-	1.00			1.00	€ 589.95	€ 589.95
35	99.1.XB1.05.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first								
			/ month	5.00				5.00		
			Total	/ month				5.00	€ 252.86	€ 1 264.30
	99.1.XB1.08	CONSTRUCTION SITE BOX FOR MEETING ROOM USE Supply and installation of a construction site box for use as a meeting room, consisting of a base structure elevated from the ground with folded steel profiles, roof and cladding with sandwich panels made of inner and outer sheet metal and central insulation, internal partitions in sandwich panels, aluminum fixtures, wooden floor covered with PVC. Complete with electrical system and electric heating/cooling, equipped with a desk, 6 chairs, furniture, and various accessories. Approximate dimensions 2.4 × 6.4 × 2.4 m. Includes transport, assembly, dismantling, cleaning, maintenance and management costs, and preparation of the support base.								
36	99.1.XB1.08.A	Price – first month								
			Total	-	1.00			1.00	€ 654.13	€ 654.13
37	99.1.XB1.08.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first								
			/ month	5.00				5.00		
			Total	/ month				5.00	€ 245.10	€ 1 225.50
38	99.2.OZ1.04	SCAFFOLDING GROUNDING CONNECTION Installation of a grounding connection for scaffolding as part of the lightning protection system (to be provided every 25 m along the scaffold plan with a minimum of two down-conductors at the ends), executed with 35 mm ² insulated copper conductor connected to a 2.5 m galvanized steel ground rod driven into the soil. Price per down-conductor.								
			a corpo	1.00				1.00		
			Total	a corpo				1.00	€ 95.14	€ 95.14
	99.2.OZ1.05	GROUNDING SYSTEM FOR CONSTRUCTION SITE Installation of a grounding system for the construction site, consisting of 2.5 m galvanized steel rods interconnected with bare 35 mm ² copper conductor, including connection to the main grounding busbar using 16 mm ² insulated cable, including excavation and backfilling.								
39	99.2.OZ1.05.A	Power up to 6 kW – 2 rods								
			a corpo	1.00				1.00		
			Total	a corpo				1.00	€ 323.20	€ 323.20
	99.2.QZ1.09	CONSTRUCTION SITE DISTRIBUTION BOARD Compensation for the use of construction site distribution boards compliant with CEI 17.13/1 (EN 60439-1) and CEI 17.13/4 (EN 60439-4) standards, with IP55 protection rating, consisting of an enclosure made of insulating, impact-resistant, and self-extinguishing material for wall installation or mounting on a self-supporting stand. Equipped with triangular-key doors to prevent access by unauthorized personnel, suitable for lockable plugs, containing internal boxes with terminal blocks, IP55 interlocked socket outlets, and boxes complete with circuit breakers with 6 kA breaking capacity and 0.03 A residual current protection. Includes connection of the supply line via external fixed plug or terminal block, emergency indicator push button installed on the external board frame complete with trip coil on the main switch, CEI 17.13/4 (EN 60439-4) certification, wiring, electrical connections, accessory works, and finishing. Includes removal at the end of use.								
40	99.2.QZ1.09.A	Board including 3 sockets 2P+T 16 A and 1 socket 3P+T 16 A Board including 3 sockets 2P+T 16 A and 1 socket 3P+T 16 A, complete with circuit breakers and 4P residual current main switch – 40 A – 0.03 A								
			/ month	6.00				6.00		
			Total	/ month				6.00	€ 43.40	€ 260.40

L2		BELOW-GROUND WORKS									
01		Excavations and backfilling									
	11.7.CP1.01	FOUNDATION EXCAVATION IN SOIL OF ANY NATURE Execution of foundation excavation in a restricted section in soil of any nature and consistency, including boulders with a volume of less than 0.5 m ³ , excluding soft rock and hard rock requiring blasting, whether dry or wet, also in the presence of water of any type, origin, and quantity, for the construction of foundations for structures in general and building foundations, for the laying of pipelines and prefabricated elements, carried out to depths of up to 2 m relative to the stripping level, including the removal of shrubs and stumps, topsoil stripping and recovery, water pumping, any necessary shoring and bracing of the sides, formation of slopes where required, loading and transport within the site of suitable excavated material, including topsoil, for backfilling and embankments, properly shaped and compacted. Any additional operations for the reuse of excavated material or the removal of material deemed unsuitable by the Works Supervisor shall be compensated separately.									
12	11.7.CP1.01.A	Also in the presence of water (water depth up to 20 cm).									
			WEST side	m3	1.79	34.04			60.86		
			EST side	m3	1.79	34.04			60.86		
			NORTH side	m3	1.79	9.03			16.15		
			SOUTH side	m3	1.79	9.03			16.15		
			Total	m3					154.02	€ 20.19 € 3 109.63	
	11.7.CP1.06	MANUAL FOUNDATION EXCAVATION IN SOIL OF ANY NATURE INSIDE BUILDINGS Execution of manual excavation for the construction of foundations for structures in general and for the laying of pipelines inside buildings, in soil of any nature and consistency, including boulders up to 0.5 m ³ and soft rock removable with pick or point tools, excluding hard rock requiring blasting, whether dry or wet, also in the presence of water of any type, origin, and quantity, for depths up to 2 m from the excavation level. This includes shoring and bracing of the sides, preservation and protection of any existing installations such as pipelines, ducts, cables, structures, archaeological finds, etc., formation of slopes, and backfilling. Any additional operations for the reuse of excavated material or the removal of material deemed unsuitable by the Works Supervisor shall be compensated separately.									
13	11.7.CP1.06.A	Also in the presence of water (water depth up to 20 cm).									
			EAST lateral rooms	m3	2.00	3.36	3.97	2.10	56.02		
			WEST lateral rooms	m3	2.00	3.91	3.96	2.10	65.03		
				m3	2.00	1.15	1.66	2.10	8.02		
			EAST central rooms	m3	2.00	3.01	3.97	2.10	50.19		
			WEST central rooms	m3	2.00	3.91	3.96	2.10	65.03		
				m3	2.00	1.15	1.66	2.10	8.02		
			Total	m3					252.31	€ 145.25 € 36 648.20	
	11.8.CP1.12	DELIVERY OF EXCAVATED MATERIAL FROM THE SITE TO AUTHORIZED TREATMENT AND RECOVERY FACILITIES Transport and delivery of inert waste material resulting from site activities to an authorized waste treatment and recovery facility, including all administrative requirements for handling, transport within a distance of up to 15 km, and delivery to the treatment plant (waste to be delivered to facilities authorized for treatment in accordance with current regulations, Legislative Decree 152/06 as amended and supplemented, and Regional Law 30/87 as amended and supplemented).									
			see item n. 13	m3	252.31				252.31		
			Total	m3					252.31	€ 46.17 € 11 649.25	
		Total Excavation and Backfilling								€ 51 407.08	
02		Structural Works									
	PA.01 (see the attached detailed price analysis)	STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – GALVANIZED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR Two-sided structural reinforcement of masonry or concrete walls using a cement plaster with a variable thickness of 30 mm to 70 mm, combined with galvanized welded wire mesh Ø6, 20x20 cm, including transverse passing-through connections 6Ø6/m ² in Ø10 holes. INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of existing plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the wall surface; drilling of holes; insertion of the transverse connections described above, at a rate of not less than 6/m ² ; application of the concrete layer, and all other operations necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with the recognized standards of workmanship EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at wall intersections with horizontal and vertical structural elements Scaffolding, platforms, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the works, as well as any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified. Application on both sides of the wall and for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. The price is applied per square meter of wall.									
			EXTERNAL WALLS	m2					0.00		
			EAST wall	m2		34.04		2.10	71.48		
			WEST wall	m2		34.04		2.10	71.48		

			NORTH wall	m2		9.03		2.10	18.96		
			SOUTH wall	m2		9.03		2.10	18.96		
									0.00		
									0.00		
			INTERNAL WALLS	m2					0.00		
			Longitudinal walls	m2	2.00	12.52		2.10	52.58		
			Trasnversal walls	m2	4.00	3.97		2.10	33.35		
				m2	4.00	2.97		2.10	24.95		
			Stairwell	m2	4.00	3.36		2.10	28.22		
				m2	4.00	5.66		2.10	47.54		
			Total	m2					367.54	€ 191.01	€ 70 204.20
16	PA.01.1 (see the attached detailed price analysis)	STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – GALVANIZED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors Two-sided structural reinforcement - galvanized steel reinforced cement mortar coating. Surcharge for the execution of the connection of the reinforced coating with the foundation and across floors, by using galvanized ribbed steel bars Ø8, B450C, applied at a rate of 4/m at both wall sides. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the coating of the reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø). INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S, or equivalent. EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified. Application on both sides of the wall. The price is applied per meter of wall.									
			EXTERNAL WALLS	m					0.00		
			EAST wall	m	2.00	34.04			68.08		
			WEST wall	m	2.00	34.04			68.08		
			NORTH wall	m	2.00	9.03			18.06		
			SOUTH wall	m	2.00	9.03			18.06		
									0.00		
			INTERNAL WALLS	m					0.00		
			Longitudinal walls	m	4.00	12.52			50.08		
			Trasnversal walls	m	8.00	3.97			31.76		
				m	8.00	2.97			23.76		
			Stairwell	m	8.00	3.36			26.88		
				m	8.00	5.66			45.28		
			Total	m					350.04	€ 24.83	€ 8 691.49
			Total Structural Works								€ 78 895.69
	03	Building Works									
	13.3.LN7.01	WATERPROOFING OF WALLS – PROTECTION WITH DRAINAGE SHEET Supply and installation of a drainage sheet for the protection of waterproofing, including fixing and overlaps.									
17	13.3.LN7.01.A	Drainage sheet 8 mm thick									
			Protection layer – Studded membrane	m2	151.60				151.60		
			Total	m2					151.60	€ 17.00	€ 2 577.20
	13.3.LS1.01	WATERPROOFING OF WALLS WITH ROOT-RESISTANT PLASTOMERIC MEMBRANE Supply and installation of an elastic, root-resistant plastomeric waterproofing membrane (sheet) with double reinforcement of polyester non-woven fabric and glass fiber mat, for waterproofing walls in contact with earth. This includes surface cleaning prior to installation, formation of a protective shell, application of two coats of fast-drying primer, flame bonding of the sheets, overlaps, and all consumables and waste material.									
18	13.3.LS1.01.A	Membrane 3 mm thick , 3 kg/m ²									
			WEST facade	m2		34.04		1.76	59.91		
			EAST facade	m2		34.04		1.76	59.91		
			NORTH facade	m2		9.03		1.76	15.89		
			SOUTH facade	m2		9.03		1.76	15.89		
			Total	m2					151.61	€ 34.66	€ 5 254.68
19	13.3.LS1.01.B	Membrane 4 mm thick , 4 kg/m ²									
			Second membrane	m2	151.60				151.60		

			Total	m2					151.60	€ 37.40	€ 5 669.84
	20.1.BQ4.01	DEMOLITION OF PLAIN OR REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES Execution of the demolition of plain or reinforced concrete structures of any shape and thickness, including any plaster, cutting of reinforcement bars, removal of pipes, necessary shoring and protective measures at any location and height, provision of work scaffolding, lowering of debris from any height or depth and transport to public disposal sites, disposal fees, use of compressors with pneumatic hammers, demolition clamps, or other demolition equipment, excluding blasting.									
20	20.1.BQ4.01.A	For unreinforced concrete									
			Opening of holes in the basement	m3	8.00	1.00	0.30	2.10	5.04		
			Total	m3					5.04	€ 274.77	€ 1 384.84
			Total building works								€ 14 886.56
			Totale BELOW-GROUND WORKS								€ 145 189.33
	L3	GENERAL WORKS									
	04	Safety									
21	99.1.AB1.01	FIRST AID KIT PACKAGE Supply of a first aid kit package compliant with D.M. 338/2003 (Annex 2); minimum contents: disposable sterile gloves (2 pairs), bottle of 10% iodine povidone skin solution, 125 ml, bottle of saline solution (0.9% sodium chloride), 250 ml, sterile gauze pads 18 x 40 cm in individual packets (1), sterile gauze pads 10 x 10 cm in individual packets (3), disposable sterile dressing forceps (1), package of absorbent cotton (1), package of adhesive plasters of various sizes ready for use (1), roll of adhesive tape 2.5 cm wide (1), roll of hemmed bandage 10 cm wide (1), one pair of scissors, tourniquet (1), package of ready-to-use ice packs (1), disposable bags for medical waste collection (1), instructions on how to use the above items and provide first aid while awaiting emergency services.									
				-	1.00				1.00		
			Total	-					1.00	€ 58.72	€ 58.72
	99.1.AH2.01	CONSTRUCTION SITE FENCING WITH ELECTROWELDED MESH AND FIXED POLES Installation of 200 cm high construction site fencing, made with scaffold tubes fixed on lean concrete footings and electrowelded metal mesh. Includes fastening the metal mesh to the poles, dismantling, and restoration of the area affected by the fencing.									
22	99.1.AH2.01.A	Price – first month		m2		200.00		2.00	400.00		
			Total	m2					400.00	€ 8.00	€ 3 200.00
23	99.1.AH2.01.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first		m2 / month	7.00	200.00		2.00	2 800.00		
			Total	m2 / month					2 800.00	€ 1.36	€ 3 808.00
	99.1.AN6.01	STAMPED PLASTIC MESH Supply and installation of stamped plastic mesh to be applied to construction site fencing, including fastening the mesh to the fence.									
24	99.1.AN6.01.A	Price – first month		m2	400.00				400.00		
			see item n. 160	m2					400.00	€ 2.89	€ 1 156.00
			Total	m2					400.00		
25	99.1.AN6.01.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first		m2 / month	2800.00				2 800.00		
			Total	m2 / month					2 800.00	€ 0.95	€ 2 660.00
	99.1.MH4.02	ALUMINUM SAFETY SIGN Supply and installation of aluminum safety sign with minimum thickness of 0.5 mm, compliant with D.Lgs. 81/2008, Title V, and UNI 7543, complete with fixings.									
26	99.1.MH4.02.A	Format "K" (visible up to 4 m)		/ month	8.00				8.00		
			Total	/ month					8.00	€ 1.30	€ 10.40
	99.1.QX1.01	PORTABLE POWDER FIRE EXTINGUISHER Supply and installation of portable powder fire extinguisher, with construction, safety devices, pressure indicators, supports, markings, color, and certification in compliance with D.M. 20/12/82. Suitable for extinguishing Class A, B, and C fires, with minimum extinguishing capacity as indicated in the sub-items. Complete with declaration of conformity to the approval document issued by the Ministry of the Interior and provided by the manufacturer, wall-mounting bracket, and signage; includes periodic maintenance as required by law.									
27	99.1.QX1.01.A	Charge 6 kg – Extinguishing capacity 34 A-233 B-C		/ month	8.00				8.00		
			Total	/ month					8.00	€ 6.15	€ 49.20

28	99.1.QX1.01.B	Charge 9 kg – Extinguishing capacity 43 A-183 B-C									
			/ month	8.00				8.00			
			Total	/ month				8.00	€ 6.51	€ 52.08	
	99.1.XB1.01	CONSTRUCTION SITE BOX FOR USE AS CHANGING ROOM DIM. 2.4 × 6.4 × 2.4 m Supply and installation of a construction site box for use as a changing room, consisting of a base structure elevated from the ground with folded steel profiles, roof and cladding with sandwich panels made of inner and outer sheet metal and central insulation (minimum 40 mm), internal partitions in sandwich panels, aluminum fixtures, wooden floor covered with PVC. Complete with electrical, water, and sewage systems, electric heating and cooling, equipped with 6 lockers with two compartments each and 6 chairs. Approximate dimensions 2.4 × 6.4 × 2.4 m. Includes transport, assembly, dismantling, cleaning, maintenance and management costs, and preparation of the support base.									
29	99.1.XB1.01.A	Price – first month									
			-	1.00				1.00			
			Total	-				1.00	€ 743.82	€ 743.82	
30	99.1.XB1.01.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first									
			/ month	7.00				7.00			
			Total	/ month				7.00	€ 280.51	€ 1 963.57	
	99.1.XB1.05	CONSTRUCTION SITE BOX FOR SANITARY FACILITIES DIM. 2.4 × 2.7 × 2.4 m Supply and installation of a construction site box for sanitary facilities, consisting of a base structure elevated from the ground with folded steel profiles, roof and cladding with sandwich panels made of inner and outer sheet metal and central insulation (minimum 40 mm), internal partitions in sandwich panels, aluminum fixtures, wooden floor covered with PVC. Complete with electrical, water (hot and cold), and sewage systems, electric heating and cooling, equipped with one shower, one WC, one washbasin, electric boiler, and accessories. Approximate dimensions 2.4 × 2.7 × 2.4 m. Includes transport, assembly, dismantling, cleaning, maintenance and management costs, and preparation of the support base.									
31	99.1.XB1.05.A	Price – first month									
			-	1.00				1.00			
			Total	-				1.00	€ 589.95	€ 589.95	
32	99.1.XB1.05.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first									
			/ month	7.00				7.00			
			Total	/ month				7.00	€ 252.86	€ 1 770.02	
	99.1.XB1.08	CONSTRUCTION SITE BOX FOR MEETING ROOM USE Supply and installation of a construction site box for use as a meeting room, consisting of a base structure elevated from the ground with folded steel profiles, roof and cladding with sandwich panels made of inner and outer sheet metal and central insulation, internal partitions in sandwich panels, aluminum fixtures, wooden floor covered with PVC. Complete with electrical system and electric heating/cooling, equipped with a desk, 6 chairs, furniture, and various accessories. Approximate dimensions 2.4 × 6.4 × 2.4 m. Includes transport, assembly, dismantling, cleaning, maintenance and management costs, and preparation of the support base.									
33	99.1.XB1.08.A	Price – first month									
			-	1.00				1.00			
			Total	-				1.00	€ 654.13	€ 654.13	
34	99.1.XB1.08.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first									
			/ month	7.00				7.00			
			Total	/ month				7.00	€ 245.10	€ 1 715.70	
35	99.2.OZ1.04	SCAFFOLDING GROUNDING CONNECTION Installation of a grounding connection for scaffolding as part of the lightning protection system (to be provided every 25 m along the scaffold plan with a minimum of two down-conductors at the ends), executed with 35 mm ² insulated copper conductor connected to a 2.5 m galvanized steel ground rod driven into the soil. Price per down-conductor.									
			a corpo	1.00				1.00			
			Total	a corpo				1.00	€ 95.14	€ 95.14	
	99.2.OZ1.05	GROUNDING SYSTEM FOR CONSTRUCTION SITE Installation of a grounding system for the construction site, consisting of 2.5 m galvanized steel rods interconnected with bare 35 mm ² copper conductor, including connection to the main grounding busbar using 16 mm ² insulated cable, including excavation and backfilling.									
36	99.2.OZ1.05.A	Power up to 6 kW – 2 rods									
			a corpo	1.00				1.00			
			Total	a corpo				1.00	€ 323.20	€ 323.20	

